

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D5.4 – Design of Personalised Prevention and Intervention Measures I

WP5 AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised
Recommendations

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Executive summary

The objective of this deliverable is to define personalised recommendations in terms of prevention and intervention measures that are targeted to specific risks associated with pancreatic cancer. Consequently, we first map the process of design and delivery of prevention and intervention measures to be applied in the project. We identify the opportunity to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) to improve the precision and personalisation of:

- The risk assessment and health recommendations to be offered to citizens/individuals from the perspective of health care professionals
- Coaching (supporting) communications to be offered to citizens/individuals receiving the recommended behaviour change recommendation within the iHelp platform.

In relation to enhancing the precision of the risk assessment interventions, we provide it based on citizens' own health, lifestyle, and biology markers. In relation to enhancing the personalisation of coaching support, we develop a personalisation framework enabling us to provide personalised communication via the coaching dialogue functionality. The coaching dialogue developed in in this deliverable is developed for the purpose of supporting goal setting stage – where iHelp can help individuals to set up specific goals. Once the framework is developed and validated, many of its principles can be applied to regular coaching activities (e.g., in health education, insights provision and support). The personalisation is enabled through development of a segmentation approach enabling iHelp to segment individuals based on their health goal orientation, level of health literacy and gender. We develop the personalisation coaching framework in the context of physical activity, and we will test feasibility of the framework before implementing it within the iHelp project.

1 Introduction and Objectives

1.1 Scope and objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to define personalised recommendations in terms of prevention and intervention measures that are targeted to specific risks associated with pancreatic cancer. This deliverable aims to explain the initial steps taken in the process of developing the personalisation approaches. We review the background, tasks and methodology undertaken to develop our personalisation framework. The report proposes an initial personalisation framework that will need to be further validated and tested within the iHelp project. In our second deliverable (D5.5 “Design of personalised prevention and intervention measures II”, due in M32) we will summarise the personalisation approaches used in each pilot together with its effectiveness.

1.2 Structure of the document

To ensure we meet the objectives associated with this task, this deliverable document defines the actors, procedures and processes that are involved in the personalisation of iHelp services.

In Section 3 we aim to illustrate personalisation from the perspective of healthcare professionals (or AI supporting their decisions) and individuals/citizens. We outline the personalisation processes supported by iHelp, identify the existing knowledge and expertise, and identify the knowledge gaps that should be addressed to ensure definition of personalised recommendations in terms of prevention and intervention measures that are targeted to specific risks associated with pancreatic cancer.

In Section 4 we focus on explaining and defining possible health recommendations [to be issued by healthcare professionals (or AI supporting their decisions) and accepted by individuals/citizens]. The iHelp platform will support:

- Delivery of those recommendations through the pancreatic cancer risk assessment approaches and
- Support in the form of coaching to individuals/citizens supporting their pursuit of the recommended health behaviours.

In Section 5 we explain the main principles guiding segmentation of individuals/citizens, which is a necessary condition needed to introduce a certain level of personalisation of coaching approaches. We report empirical evidence supporting the relevance of the proposed typology for acceptance of health behaviours, physical activity. Part of the empirical inquiry involved collecting written responses from individuals in relation to their barriers and motivations to engage in a specific health behaviour.

In Section 6 we explain empirical work undertaken to validate the proposed segmentation framework and provide further information in relation to the identified groups/segments.

In Section 7 we build on the main findings in relation to personalisation and propose an overarching framework that could guide execution of the personalisation rules and principles developed so far. We outline the main characteristics of message content that could appeal differently to segments identified by us earlier

In Section 8 we propose sample dialogues to be considered for implementation in the iHelp project.

Finally, in Section 9 we outline the future work and planned improvement and validation of the proposed framework for coaching dialogue development which will be tested and validated before full implementation in the iHelp platform.

1.3 Relevance with other WPs

Developing this framework is especially relevant for the project pilots, as planned in WP4 Knowledge Management and Utilisation in the iHelp Platform and WP6 iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies. Personalised approaches are very important in ensuring that the health interventions are understood and more likely to be accepted by individuals. To ensure that the personalisation is taking place at various levels (e.g., intervention, user interfaces, coaching, feedback), the personalisation framework is developed together with other iHelp partners involved in WP4 (“Knowledge Management and Utilisation in the iHelp Platform”), WP5 (“AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised Recommendations”) and WP6 (“iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”).

2 Interaction with other tasks

The T5.2 (“Design of Personalised Prevention and Intervention Measures”) focuses on applying the personalisation of intervention approaches methodology to the specific interventions as planned to be delivered by the pilot partners in the iHelp project. The personalisation framework is designed to increase precision and acceptance of the iHelp recommendations aiming to reduce risks of pancreatic cancer. Consequently, the measures and framework are developed for the purpose of all the efforts in relation to activities undertaken by pilot partners, as planned in T6.1 (“Scientific Coordination of Validation and Pilot Scenarios”) in WP6 (“iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”) and supported by T2.4 (“User Centred Design”) in WP2 (“Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios in iHelp”), T4.1 (“Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions”) and T4.2 (“Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models”) in WP4 (“Knowledge Management and Utilisation in the iHelp Platform”) and T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanism for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback”) and T5.5 (“Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms”) in WP5 (“AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised Recommendations”).

2.1 Relationship with tasks within WP4 and WP6

To make sure the proposed framework addresses the needs of the specific interventions, it is developed with a close collaboration with pilot partners developing their work in WP4 (“Knowledge Management and Utilisation in the iHelp Platform”) and WP6 (“iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”). Understanding the specificity of each intervention as used by each pilot, as described in T6.1 (“Scientific Coordination of Validation and Pilot Scenarios”), enables us to understand the type of activities and behaviours to be recommended within each pilot. Understanding the AI decision support techniques to enable the design of personalised recommendations (prevention and intervention measures) designed for WP6 iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies based on the modelling techniques in T4.1 (“Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions”) and analytic workbench in T4.2 (“Model Library: Implementation and Recalibration of Adaptive Models”) helps us ensure the proposed framework is feasible from the perspective of technology.

As most of the recommended behaviours (in WP6 (“iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”)) will relate to lifestyle choice and changes (e.g., encouraging people to be more active, quit smoking or introduce a healthier diet), we consulted the literature and expertise within the iHelp consortium in relation to the challenges with such recommendations. Consequently, our framework considers specific needs and challenges that are likely to be faced by our pilot partners.

2.2 Relationships with other tasks within WP5

We work together with T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanism for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback”) as this iHelp partner enables us to execute the proposed personalisation framework using the technology platform of iHelp. This task delivers the user-centric smart applications to support the delivery of personalized healthcare through the use of mobile, IoT and wearable technologies. Together with T5.3 we will design and validate various scenarios and deployment configurations to be used by virtual assistant (coaching agent). Thus, the virtual assistant will not be limited to giving standardized health advice to patients, rather it will be based on continuous analysis of patient’s characteristics, personalisation

approaches and responses to various support initiatives aiming provide multiple feedback to the patient according to his/her healthcare needs.

We also work together with T5.5 (“Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms”). This task develops the mechanisms for monitoring, alerting and feedback gathering through the user-centric application developed in T5.3. In addition to providing increased level of health awareness by monitoring multiple health parameters (and making them available to the users of the application), the monitoring mechanisms developed in this task are specifically designed to track and/or monitor the impact of targeted recommendations (interventions-prevention measures) that are prescribed to individuals by the clinician/medical-experts. Consequently, the functionality provided by T5.3 and T5.5. will enable to optimise the designed personalisation algorithms and ensure that we collect any piece of data that can support functionality and effectiveness of iHelp interventions.

2.3 Relationships with task T2.4

To ensure that the user interfaces that will be used to deliver our personalisation intervention are supporting our work we work with T2.4 (“User Centred Design”) in WP2 (“Requirements, State of the Art Analysis and User Scenarios”) in iHelp. This task will apply user centred design process and design thinking methodology to provide the user-centred design principles that will guide the design and development activities in the iHelp project. A user-centered design approach in iHelp will serve to satisfyingly analyse problems and challenges, communicate ideas and involve end-users in the solution development process. Ensuring that the user interfaces developed for iHelp help in successfully reaching and facilitating interaction and engagement with different users is a very important factors contributing to the success of the personalisation approach.

2.4 Relationship with WP7

The personalisation approaches developed in T5.2 will become part of the impact assessment of the iHelp project – to be carried out in WP7. The personalisation aspects of the iHelp platform will be assessed in nearly all tasks of the WP7 to provide a holistic view on the usefulness and usability of the developed solutions. However, a specific T7.4 (“Assessment of Sociophysical, Human and Societal Factors”) specifically focusing on evaluating the personalisation techniques designed and implemented in the context of technology solutions. T7.4 will be guided by the personalisation guidelines stipulated in this deliverable, D5.4.

3 AI and personalization in the context of health recommendations

Artificial Intelligence (AI) relates to the use of a wide range of computer science solutions that aim to build smart machines that can perform tasks typically requiring human intelligence (N., S., K., +18A). At the heart of artificial intelligence is decision-making with different AI methodologies approaching the problem in different ways (S., N., 19). AI solutions are often developed based on existing datasets explaining a typical decision and factors contributing to it. AI then makes decisions based on data fed into a model to develop an algorithm – a set of rules to make predictions. As the AI enabled solutions are used (e.g., an app or a website utilising an AI algorithm to support a given decision), new data resulting from real case scenarios utilising the AI algorithm becomes available. This new data in the context of AI-supported decisions can then be used to finetune and optimise the existing AI algorithms. As more data becomes available, the machines (e.g., an app or a website) can become more and more precise in the decision support it provides (N., S., K., +18B).

3.1 AI support for physician decisions and recommendations

In the context of healthcare, predominant use of AI algorithms is used to increase precision of medical recommendations. To illustrate this scenario, we can imagine a computer (an app or a website) showing intelligence enabling it to support medical decisions. AI could resemble a physician who speaks to a patient, examines his/her, and based on the collected information can provide a diagnosis and provide a list of recommendations for the patient. Recommendations can involve changes to someone's lifestyle (e.g., being more active, eating more healthily, taking certain supplements, prescription of medication(s) or suggestions of further tests and diagnostics). In this case, AI can support decision-making from the perspective of a physician, and personalisation of the AI algorithms means that the recommendations involve the patient's own (versus population-based) body metrics.

It is important to note that in this context of AI application, due to ethical implications, reliability of data and stability of various predictive algorithms, AI is recommended to support physician's decisions, not replace physicians. In healthcare, numerous principles guide decision-making from evidence-based practice to ethics. Four prima facie ethical principles guide healthcare workers through the complex moral landscape of caring for other humans – respect for autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice (GIL94). The adoption of AI within healthcare must adhere to these principles, whilst dealing with new moral issues that inherently arise from using this technology in this space. When the data used to develop algorithms are based on homogenous datasets that only narrowly represent one group of individuals, applying such algorithms to the wider population may not only result in inaccurate recommendations but has the potential to be extremely harmful. Numerous cases have been documented in the literature including a case of AI that was trained to detect a type of skin cancer from a dataset largely composed of Caucasian patients. Such an AI would vastly underperform in brown or black skin (N., S., K., + 18C). Technically, it is understandable how AI may excel in identifying visual differences in images of dark lesions on Caucasian skin, but ethically, such an AI could lead to potentially fatal outcomes for people with brown or black skin and exacerbate long-standing health inequalities. To compound this further, AI may create black box scenarios whereby explain ability in clinical decision-making is lost due to the advanced methodologies AI

uses. Being able to explain clinical decision-making is fundamental to a trusting doctor-patient relationship; informed consent; the legal framework of clinical practice; and ultimately evidence-based practice and scientific inquiry.

3.2 AI support for a citizen's health decisions

There is another application of AI algorithms in the context of healthcare, which received much less attention from both academics and practitioners. In order for physician's recommendations (see the above paragraph about using AI to personalise and increase precision of physician's decisions) to be effective, it requires a citizen's decisions to accept the physician's/health recommendations (e.g., being more active, eating more healthily, taking certain supplements, prescription of medication(s) or suggestions of further tests and diagnostics) and make the recommended health behaviour part of one's day or lifestyle. As health recommendations might often require time, effort or sacrifices from individuals/patients, acceptance of health recommendations proves challenging, as for many the recommended changes interfere too much with one's life, lifestyle or beliefs and knowledge about one's own health.

From the health psychology point of view, the key to issuing health recommendations that are likely to bring about the desired behaviour change is by carefully crafted health messages that could use most convincing arguments, message framing, timing, etc. In most cases, design and targeting of the messages is developed in relation to a group of people with a specific health condition (e.g., those with diabetes, intending to lose weight, etc.). From the perspective of marketing, there is scope to personalise recommendations in how different messages are used to target different groups of individuals - considering various lifestyle related needs and goals, and a specific intervention to be used. This approach enables matching of message content (e.g., health recommendations, coaching dialogues to be used by virtual agents supporting behaviour change attempts) to specific needs of a particular group of similar individuals (segment). The main principle of matching message content to different segments is that people in different segments are likely to show similar needs in relation to the intervention under consideration. By using the message content that matches (or is compatible) with lifestyle and goal-related needs of a segment, the recommended behaviour is more likely to be appreciated and accepted. Once initial personalisation rules are developed, it can be used to support individual progression with the behaviour change journey (i.e., when used in a mobile app or a website). As the rules are implemented, messages used and acted upon, some of the initial rules and algorithms can become fine-tuned and increase precision of coaching and support given to the individual who is in the process of behaviour change (e.g., when someone aims to introduce a more active lifestyle).

While this type of citizen's personalisation is typically used in marketing for commercial products and services, it is not typically used in the healthcare domain. One of the reasons for such a limitation might be the fact that for such personalisation approaches to be effective, they should consider the desirable behaviour (e.g., increase in physical activity), a specific intervention (e.g., health advice based on a certain test, risk assessment for a given disease or one's genetic profile) and segmentation/profiling approach should be developed based on those factors. Consequently, developing such personalisation approaches could require various type of resources that are often scarce in the healthcare systems. Furthermore, the number of potential behaviours to be addressed and interventions to be used opened a need for development of multiple personalisation approaches, each supporting different behaviour and health intervention. However, if such approaches are developed for the most common behaviours that act as a

risk factor for various chronic diseases, especially pancreatic cancer (e.g., physical activity, healthy diet) - it could be further optimised to account for more behaviours and interventions.

3.3 iHelp context: pancreatic cancer risk prediction as an intervention used to deliver health recommendations and coaching to citizens

Building on the background explained in the sections 3.1 and 3.2. above, design of personalised prevention and intervention measures for the iHelp project involves personalisation of health recommendations from both the physician's and citizen's perspective.

Personalisation from the physician's perspective is grounded in recognising pancreatic cancer risk factors impacting one's likelihood to have pancreatic cancer in the future. Healthcare practitioners with the support of AI algorithms used by iHelp can evaluate risk of having pancreatic cancer for a single individual and based on that risk estimation provide personalised (to one's health, lifestyle, and genetic profile) recommendations for healthy behaviours to be undertaken to reduce the risk of being ill in the future (e.g., eating more healthily or being more physically active).

Personalisation from the citizen's perspective is grounded in recognising the motivations and challenges to undertake recommended healthy behaviours (e.g., eating more healthily or being more physically active) by different groups of people (segments) and personalising behaviour change communication and coaching to account for:

- Specific health and lifestyle need of each segment
- The recommended behaviour to change/engage with (e.g., eating more healthily or being more physically active)
- The specific health intervention to be used (in iHelp risk factors to develop pancreatic cancer in the future).

3.3.1 AI precision of pancreatic cancer risk assessment in the iHelp project

AI in iHelp will be used to optimise precision of assessing individual risk of developing pancreatic cancer in the future. For UNIMAN pilot, the group has developed an initial risk prediction model. Using this model will enable us to assess risk and classify people into low, medium and high-risk groups, as illustrated in Figure 1 below. The model applies regression with binary outcome to seek the best fit model that could predict pancreatic cancer risk. These risk factors (e.g., smoking, physical activity, diet, etc.) included in the model were first tested for their association with pancreatic cancer risk. Next, we fitted the model and tested further for model specification, correlation amongst risk factors. Once the model was defined, we applied bootstrap method (1000 iterations) to obtain estimated value for model validation. Model calibration also obtained using expected and observed % of group probability and chi square test was performed. Model calibration is also displayed as a graphic image.

We will use other sources of data to do the further external calibration. After the external calibration is confirmed performing well, the risk prediction model can be widely used by other European Union (EU)

partners. For all pilot studies, they will collect data and feed the data back to the technical partners. The AI approach will be used to generate and optimise an appropriate risk prediction suitable for different audiences. The ultimate goal is to utilise AI to enable the system to reason and learn and empowers decision making through augmented intelligence.

Figure 1: Illustration of risk assessment process to be deployed in iHelp

Within the UNIMAN pilot, an additional level of risk assessment/personalisation of health recommendations will be delivery of genetic profiling to individuals categorised to be at high risk of developing pancreatic risk in the future.

3.3.1.1 Feasibility and effectiveness of genetic risk assessment interventions

Current studies support that providing genomic risk information in the community is feasible and appropriate. The Predicting Risk of Cancer at Screening (PROCAS) study (V., B., B., 18) (H., T., G., 20) has shown the role of Protocol Registration and Results System (PRS) in risk predictions in the community, and the Australia study also adds the evidence that performing a genomic test in primary care without concerns. Furthermore, one Randomized Control Trial (RCT) trial (SEN, 17) has also addressed the issue that providing personalised genomic risk information to people might have the potential to improve prevention behaviours.

In the PROCAS study, they have shown that combining a PRS with standard risk factors and measures of mammographic density may provide more accurate risk predictions that substantially increase the proportion of women at high and moderate risk of breast cancer (>5% 10-year risk aged ≥46 years) as well as those at low-risk (≤2% 10-year risk). These studies demonstrated the validation and implementation of using PRS in risk stratification to guide community surveillance recommendations.

One Australia study using Colorectal Cancer (CRC) genomic test (PRS score) (S., M., W., 21) also showed evidence that performing genomic tests does not pose a significant concern to patients in community settings. This study initially provided 150 General Practitioners (GP) patients with the pre-test counselling (approximately 5–10 min), and then recorded their informed decision-making and attitude. Their result revealed that with a brief discussion of its implications, most participants (95%) were able to make an

informed decision about a genomic test for CRC risk even in the participants with inadequate knowledge. 73% made an informed choice about the test, in addition, most had positive attitudes towards the test offered and the vast majority chose to do the test. Therefore, this study provides us with another evidence that performing such a genomic test and making inform-decision in primary care may be feasible and appropriate.

In addition, a randomised control study conducted by Smith (SEN., 09), it recruited 119 people to discover the feasibility, acceptability, and impact for communication of personalised melanoma genomic risk information. After collecting saliva samples, the participants were randomly allocated to the control group (not provide personalised genomic risk information) and the intervention group (provide personalised genomic risk information). Their result indicated that providing information on the personalised genomic risk of melanoma to the public could improve preventive behaviours. Furthermore, there was no evidence of adverse psychological outcomes in this study.

3.3.1.2 Biological age as a genetic intervention to be used with individuals categorised at high risk

DNA methylation, one of the epigenetic biomarkers, has been a valid surrogate for biological age, and will be utilised in UNIMAN pilot, as illustrated in Figure 1 above. The current studies demonstrated robust results with a change in biological age by interventions. Therefore, we can well explain to our participants that there is a possible slowdown of epigenetic ageing and the potential reversibility of the ageing effect by modifying one's lifestyle.

A randomized, controlled clinical trial conducted by Fitzgerald (F., H., H., +21) demonstrates a potential reversal of biological age. In this study, they recruited 43 males (ages of 50-72) without a history of recent or chronic disease and then randomized sorted into treatment and control groups. The participants in the treatment group were instructed to begin the 8-week intervention protocol including dietary, supplement, and lifestyle changes (30 minutes of exercise per day for at least 5 days, a minimum of 7 hours sleep per day, and doing breathing exercise). They used Horvath's clock of DNA methylation to represent biological age. Their result demonstrates that participants in the treatment group had 3.23 years younger biological age after this 8-week intervention program. The other randomized factorial intervention trial "Diet, Physical Activity, and Mammography (DAMA)" (F., C., P., +21) consists of 219 healthy postmenopausal women also concluded that improving dietary quality and increasing physical activity can slow down the epigenetic ageing processes. This study distributed the participants into four trial study arms (arm 1: dietary intervention, arm 2: PA intervention, arm 3: dietary +PA intervention, and arm 4: control group) and then last for 24 months. DNAmGrim Age Acceleration (DNAmGrimAA) and Epigenetic Mutation Load (EML) were set as the measurement of epigenetic biomarkers. Their result revealed that the dietary intervention led to a significant reduction of DNAmGrimAA, whereas the physical activity intervention caused a significant reduction of the EML.

3.3.2 AI personalisation of coaching supporting citizen's health decisions

For the purpose of supporting individuals in pursuing the health recommendations they were given following the risk assessment (e.g., engaging in physical activity), iHELP will provide coaching support, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2 (see below).

We consider a **health recommendation** to be specific health behaviour as recommended in the initial stage of risk assessment (see details in Figure 2 below)

We consider a **coaching dialogue content** to be anything that a digital virtual coach can say to the user that relates to his/her health. In practice, we are always talking about a small (or large) "dialogue" which is defined using the WOOL Dialogue Language.

A certain level of automation can be used to personalise coaching content, and when it comes to supporting the behaviours recommended following risk assessment, as illustrated in Figure 2 below. There is scope to personalise coaching content in how different messages are used to target different groups of individuals - considering various lifestyle related needs and goals, and a specific intervention to be used. This approach enables matching of message content to specific needs of a particular group of similar individuals (segment). The main principle of matching message content to different segments is that people in different segments are likely to show similar needs in relation to the intervention under consideration. By using the message content that matches (or is compatible) with lifestyle and goal-related needs of a segment, the recommended behaviour (which coaching is concerned with) is more likely to be appreciated and accepted.

Figure 2: Illustration of personalised coaching

As this type of personalisation is not typically used in the healthcare domain, part of T5.2 (“Design of Personalised Prevention and Intervention Measures”) of defining personalised recommendations in terms of prevention and intervention measures in relation to pancreatic cancer involves developing grounds for such personalisation approaches. If such approaches are developed for the most common behaviours that act as a risk factor for various chronic diseases, especially pancreatic cancer (e.g., physical activity, healthy diet) - it could be further optimised to account for more behaviours and interventions.

Consequently, the remaining parts of this deliverable focus on outlining the work and process of development of personalised coaching approaches development.

4 Developing personalised coaching approaches

Personalisation from the coaching perspective is enabled by recognising the motivations and challenges to undertake recommended healthy behaviours (e.g., eating more healthily or being more physically active) by different groups of people (segments) and personalising behaviour change communication and coaching to account for:

- Specific health and lifestyle need of each segment
- The recommended behaviour to change/engage with (e.g., eating more healthily or being more physically active)
- The specific health intervention to be used (in iHelp risk factors to develop pancreatic cancer in the future).

To design such personalisation approaches, in sections below we review the relevant recommended health behaviours, together with specific tactics. Because there is a range of healthy behaviours, in this deliverable report (and initial implementation) we focused on physical activity, listed as one of the most relevant risk factors for many diseases, including pancreatic cancer. Validating the personalisation approach in the aspect of one specific activity (here physical activity) enables us to use the approach in the context of different behaviours, such as leading a healthy diet or healthy sleep management.

Following the review of the recommended behaviours, in section 4.4 we review the most relevant individual factors that are likely to impact individual needs and health goals. We identify health goal orientation, level of health literacy and gender as the main personal characteristics that are likely to impact on acceptance of health behaviours in the context of disease risk assessment (goal orientation is a specific type of motivation that is predicted to behave in certain ways under conditions of higher/lower risk).

Considering the ethical implications of health recommendations and coaching (see section 3.1) as well as rare utilisation of such personalisation practices in the context of healthcare (see section 3.2), the proposed coaching dialogues ideas will need to be validated in empirical research, before being implemented in the iHelp pilots.

4.1 Scope of recommended behaviours and specific tactics

Various healthcare organisations provide a list of recommendations and specific tactics in relation to some lifestyle changes that are likely to have the most impact on health promotion and disease prevention. In the sections below we review some common recommendations for physical activity, diet, and sleep. We then delve deeper into physical activity, reviewing specific and personalised recommendations for different groups (based on some demographic and health factors) and evidence of effectiveness of introducing such activities on one's health and disease prevention. Understanding benefits of the activity at such granular level can enable us to develop more precise and targeted coaching dialogues for the iHelp coaching. As explained before, after validating this type of personalisation approach on the example of one specific activity, here physical activity, we will apply the personalisation principles to other activities.

4.1.1 Activity 1: Physical activity

Current systematic reviews and meta-analyses have demonstrated a positive relationship between physical activity and premature mortality and the primary and secondary prevention of several chronic medical

conditions. Furthermore, clinically relevant health benefits can be accrued by simply becoming more physically active. Enclosed is the video abstract of Health benefits of physical activity¹.

The initial health assessment for all the participants will be performed. Our suggestion will be adjusted by the participants' medical conditions or concerns. We will also make sure all the activities and their intensity are appropriate for participants' fitness. Pregnant women, critical illness participants and people who had the contraindications to doing exercise will all be excluded in this trial. Our personalised recommendation will follow the National Health Service (NHS) guideline:

- Do strengthening activities that work all the major muscle groups (legs, hips, back, abdomen, chest, shoulders, and arms) at least 2 days a week.
- Do at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity activity a week or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity activity a week.
- Spread exercise evenly over 4 to 5 days a week, or every day.
- Reduce time spent sitting or lying down and break up long periods of not moving with some activity.
- Several short sessions of very vigorous-intensity activity weekly.
- A mix of moderate, vigorous, and very vigorous-intensity activity weekly.

Table 1: Descriptive caption, clearly describing the information presented in the table

Term	Definition
Physical activity terms and definitions	
Aerobic physical activity	Activity in which the body's large muscles move in a rhythmic manner for a sustained period of time. Aerobic activity – also called endurance activity – improves cardiorespiratory fitness. <i>Examples include walking, running, swimming, and bicycling.</i>
Anaerobic physical activity	Anaerobic physical activity consists of brief intense bursts of exercise, such as weightlifting and sprints, where oxygen demand surpasses oxygen supply
Bone-strengthening activity	Physical activity primarily designed to increase the strength of specific sites in bones that make up the skeletal system. Bone-strengthening activities produce an impact or tension force on the bones that promotes bone growth and strength. <i>Running, jumping rope, and lifting weights are examples of bone-strengthening activities.</i>
Domains of physical activity	Physical activity levels can be assessed in various domains, including one of more of the following: leisure-time, occupation, education, household and/or transportation.
Exercise	A subcategory of physical activity that is planned, structured, repetitive, and purposeful in the sense that the improvement or maintenance of one or more

¹ <http://links.lww.com/HCO/A42>

	<p>components of physical fitness is the objective. “Exercise” and “exercise training” frequently are used interchangeably and generally refer to physical activity performed during leisure time with the primary purpose of improving or maintaining physical fitness, physical performance, or health.</p>
Functional exercises	<p>Exercises that can be embedded into everyday tasks to improve lower-body strength, balance, and motor performance.</p> <p><i>Examples include tandem and one-leg stands, squatting, chair stands, toe raises, and stepping over obstacles.</i></p>
Household domain physical activity	<p>Physical activity undertaken in the home for domestic duties</p> <p><i>(Such as cleaning, caring for children, gardening etc.).</i></p>
Leisure-domain physical activity	<p>Physical activity performed by an individual that is not required as an essential activity of daily living and is performed at the discretion of the individual.</p> <p><i>Such activities include sports participation, exercise conditioning or training, and recreational activities such as going for a walk, dancing, and gardening.</i></p>
Light-intensity physical activity	<p>Light-intensity physical activity is between 1.5 and 3 Metabolic Equivalent of Tasks (METs), i.e., activities with energy cost less than 3 times the energy expenditure at rest for that person.</p> <p><i>This can include slow walking, bathing, or other incidental activities that do not result in a substantial increase in heart rate or breathing rate.</i></p>
Moderate-intensity physical activity	<p>On an absolute scale, moderate intensity refers to the physical activity that is performed between 3 and less than 6 times the intensity of rest. On a scale relative to an individual’s personal capacity, moderate-intensity physical activity is usually a 5 or 6 on a scale of 0–10.</p>
Muscle-strengthening activity	<p>Physical activity and exercise that increase skeletal muscle strength, power, endurance, and mass</p> <p><i>(e.g., strength training, resistance training, or muscular strength and endurance exercises).</i></p>
Multicomponent physical activity	<p>For older adults, multicomponent physical activity is important to improve physical function and decrease the risk of falls or injury from a fall. These activities can be done at home or in a structured group setting. Many studied interventions combine all types of exercise</p> <p><i>(Aerobic, muscle strengthening, and balance training) into a session, and this has been shown to be effective. An example of a multicomponent physical activity programme could include walking (aerobic activity), lifting weights (muscle strengthening), and incorporates balance training.</i></p>

	<i>Examples of balance training can include walking backwards or sideways or standing on one foot while doing an upper body muscle-strengthening activity, such as bicep curls. Dancing also combines aerobic and balance components.</i>
Sport	Sport covers a range of activities performed within a set of rules and undertaken as part of leisure or competition. Sporting activities involve physical activity carried out by teams or individuals and may be supported by an institutional framework, such as a sporting agency.
Transport domain physical activity	Physical activity performed for the purpose of getting to and from places, and refers to <i>walking, cycling, and wheeling</i> (the use of non-motorized means of locomotion with wheels, such as scooters, rollerblades, manual wheelchair etc.)
Vigorous-intensity physical activity	On an absolute scale, vigorous intensity refers to physical activity that is performed at 6.0 or more METS. On a scale relative to an individual's personal capacity, vigorous-intensity physical activity is usually a 7 or 8 on a scale of 0–10.
Work domain physical activity	Physical activity undertaken during paid or voluntary work.
Terms and definitions relating to sedentary behaviours	
Recreational screen time	Time spent watching screens (Television (TV), computer, mobile devices) for purposes other than those related to education/study or work.
Sedentary screen time	Time spent watching screen-based entertainment (TV, computer, mobile devices). Does not include active screen-based games where physical activity or movement is required
Sedentary behaviour	<p>Any waking behaviour characterized by an energy expenditure of 1.5 METS or lower while sitting, reclining, or lying. Most desk-based office work, driving a car, and watching television are examples of sedentary behaviours; these can also apply to those unable to stand, such as wheelchair users.</p> <p>The guidelines operationalize the definition of sedentary behaviour to include self-reported low movement sitting (leisure time, occupational, and total), television (TV viewing or screen time, and low levels of movement measured by devices that assess movement or posture)</p>
Terms and definitions relating to health status	
Cardiometabolic health	The interplay of blood pressure, blood lipids, blood glucose and insulin on health.
Cardiorespiratory fitness (endurance)	A health-related component of physical fitness. The ability of the circulatory and respiratory systems to supply oxygen during sustained physical activity.

	Usually expressed as measured or estimated maximal oxygen uptake (VO ₂ max).
Cognitive function	Cerebral activities, i.e., reasoning, memory, attention, and language that lead to the attainment of information and knowledge. This can also include learning.
Disability	From the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health, an umbrella term for impairments, activity limitations, and participation restrictions, denoting the negative aspects of the interaction between an individual (with a health condition) and that individual's contextual factors (environmental and personal factors).
Executive function	Includes constructs such as: working memory, cognitive flexibility (also called flexible thinking) and inhibitory control (which includes self-control).
Fitness	A measure of the body's ability to function efficiently and effectively in work and leisure activities, and includes, for example, physical fitness and cardiorespiratory fitness.
Flexibility	<p>A health- and performance-related component of physical fitness that is the range of motion possible at a joint.</p> <p>Flexibility is specific to each joint and depends on a number of specific variables including, but not limited to, the tightness of specific ligaments and tendons.</p> <p>Flexibility exercises enhance the ability of a joint to move through its full range of motion.</p>
Major muscle groups	Major muscle groups include the legs, back, abdomen, chest, shoulders, and arms.
Metabolic equivalent of task (MET)	<p>The metabolic equivalent of task, or simply metabolic equivalent, is a physiological measure expressing the intensity of physical activities.</p> <p>One MET is the energy equivalent expended by an individual while seated at rest.</p>
Psychosocial health	Include mental, emotional, and social dimensions of health.
Source: WHO Guidelines on Physical activity and sedentary behaviour, World Health Organisation, 2020	

4.1.2 Recommendations tailored to different groups

In the sections below we review the specific recommendations in relation to physical activity to different groups (see group characteristics in sections a-g below). Because some of the coaching content we will be developing should build on best and validated practices, the World Health Organization (WHO)

recommendations are in the same form as it appears in the report. This will allow us to use the most appropriate and on target phases for the coaching dialogues.

An important element of personalisation will involve personalising the advice in relation to individual health state. Consequently, part of our AI solution will be recognising the individual characteristics – as explained by the group – providing personalised recommendations (e.g., adjusting the recommended time of activity to that recommended by the guidelines), and providing encouraging comments to facilitate acceptance of this specific health recommendation (i.e., in case when individual receives a recommendation to be more active).

4.1.2.1 Children and adolescents

Benefits Of Physical Activity

According to WHO, in children and adolescents, physical activity confers benefits for the following health outcomes: improved physical fitness (cardiorespiratory and muscular fitness), cardiometabolic health (blood pressure, dyslipidaemia, glucose, and insulin resistance), bone health, cognitive outcomes (academic performance, executive function), mental health (reduced symptoms of depression); and reduced adiposity.

Recommendations

- It is recommended that this group do at least an average of 60 minutes per day of moderate to vigorous-intensity, mostly aerobic, physical activity, across the week.
- Vigorous-intensity aerobic activities, as well as those that strengthen muscle and bone, should be incorporated at least 3 days a week.

Good Practice Statements

- Doing some physical activity is better than doing none.
- If children and adolescents are not meeting the recommendations, doing some physical activity will benefit their health.
- Children and adolescents should start by doing small amounts of physical activity, and gradually increase the frequency, intensity, and duration over time.
- It is important to provide all children and adolescents with safe and equitable opportunities, and encouragement, to participate in physical activities that are enjoyable, offer variety, and are appropriate for their age and ability.

Behaviours To Avoid

- In children and adolescents, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: increased adiposity; poorer cardiometabolic health, fitness, behavioural conduct/pro-social behaviour; and reduced sleep duration.
- Children and adolescents should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary, particularly the amount of recreational screen time.

4.1.2.2 Adults (18-64 years)

Benefits Of Physical Activity

According to WHO, in adults, physical activity confers benefits for the following health outcomes: improved all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality, incident hypertension, incident site-specific cancers,2

incident type-2 diabetes, mental health (reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression); cognitive health, and sleep; measures of adiposity may also improve.

Recommendations

It is recommended that:

- All adults should undertake regular physical activity.
- Adults should do at least 150– 300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 75–150 minutes of vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity throughout the week, for substantial health benefits.

For additional health benefits adults

- Should also do muscle strengthening activities at moderate or greater intensity that involve all major muscle groups on 2 or more days a week, as these provide additional health benefits
- May increase moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity to more than 300 minutes; or do more than 150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity throughout the week for additional health benefits.

Good Practice Statements

- Doing some physical activity is better than doing none.
- If adults are not meeting these recommendations, doing some physical activity will benefit their health.
- Adults should start by doing small amounts of physical activity, and gradually increase the frequency, intensity, and duration over time.

Behaviours To Avoid

In adults, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality and cancer mortality and incidence of cardiovascular disease, cancer, and type-2 diabetes.

It is recommended that

- Adults should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.
- To help reduce the detrimental effects of high levels of sedentary behaviour on health, adults should aim to do more than the recommended levels of moderate- to vigorous-intensity physical activity.

4.1.2.3 Older adults (aged 65 years and older)

Benefits Of Physical Activity

In older adults, physical activity confers benefits for the following health outcomes: improved all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality, incident hypertension, incident site-specific cancers, incident type-2 diabetes, mental health (reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression), cognitive health, and sleep; measures of adiposity may also improve. In older adults, physical activity helps prevent falls and falls-related injuries and declines in bone health and functional ability.

Recommendations

It is recommended that:

- All older adults should undertake regular physical activity.
- Older adults should do at least 150– 300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 75–150 minutes of vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity throughout the week, for substantial health benefits.

For additional health benefits adults

- Older adults should also do muscle strengthening activities at moderate or greater intensity that involve all major muscle groups on 2 or more days a week, as these provide additional health benefits.
- As part of their weekly physical activity, older adults should do varied multicomponent physical activity that emphasises functional balance and strength training at moderate or greater intensity, on 3 or more days a week, to enhance functional capacity and to prevent falls.
- Older adults may increase moderate intensity aerobic physical activity to more than 300 minutes; or do more than 150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous intensity activity throughout the week, for additional health benefits.

Good Practice Statements

- Doing some physical activity is better than doing none.
- If older adults are not meeting the recommendations, doing some physical activity will bring benefits to health.
- Older adults should start by doing small amounts of physical activity, and gradually increase the frequency, intensity, and duration over time.
- Older adults should be as physically active as their functional ability allows and adjust their level of effort for physical activity relative to their level of fitness.

Behaviours To Avoid

In older adults, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality and cancer mortality, and incidence of cardiovascular disease, cancer, and incidence of type-2 diabetes

It is recommended that:

- Older adults should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.
- To help reduce the detrimental effects of high levels of sedentary behaviour on health, older adults should aim to do more than the recommended levels of moderate- to vigorous intensity physical activity.

4.1.2.4 Pregnant and postpartum women

Benefits Of Physical Activity

In pregnant and postpartum women, physical activity during pregnancy and postpartum confers benefits on the following maternal and foetal health benefits: decreased risk of pre-eclampsia, gestational hypertension, gestational diabetes, excessive gestational weight gain, delivery complications and postpartum depression, and fewer newborn complications, no adverse effects on birthweight; and no increase in risk of stillbirth.

Recommendations

It is recommended that all pregnant and postpartum women without contraindication should:

- Undertake regular physical activity throughout pregnancy and postpartum.
- Do at least 150 minutes of moderate intensity aerobic physical activity throughout the week for substantial health benefits.
- Incorporate a variety of aerobic and muscle strengthening activities. Adding gentle stretching may also be beneficial.
- Additionally, women who, before pregnancy, habitually engaged in vigorous intensity aerobic activity, or who were physically active, can continue these activities during pregnancy and the postpartum period.

Good Practice Statements

- Doing some physical activity is better than doing none.
- If pregnant and postpartum women are not meeting the recommendations, doing some physical activity will benefit their health.
- Pregnant and postpartum women should start by doing small amounts of physical activity, and gradually increase frequency, intensity, and duration over time.
- Pelvic floor muscle training may be performed on a daily basis to reduce the risk of urinary incontinence.

Additional safety considerations for pregnant women when undertaking physical activity are:

- Avoid physical activity during excessive heat, especially with high humidity.
- Stay hydrated by drinking water before, during, and after physical activity.
- Avoid participating in activities which involve physical contact; pose a high risk of falling; or might limit oxygenation (such as activities at high altitude, when not normally living at high altitude).
- Avoid activities in supine position after the first trimester of pregnancy.
- When considering athletic competition or exercising significantly above the recommended guidelines pregnant women should seek supervision from a specialist health-care provider.
- Pregnant women should be informed by their health-care provider of the danger signs alerting them as to when to stop; or to limit physical activity and consult a qualified health-care provider immediately should they occur.
- Return to physical activity gradually after delivery, and in consultation with a health-care provider, in the case of delivery by Caesarean section.

Behaviours To Avoid

In pregnant and postpartum women, as in all adults, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality and cancer mortality and incidence of cardiovascular disease, cancer and incidence of type-2 diabetes.

It is recommended that:

- Pregnant and postpartum women should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.

4.1.2.5 Adults and older adults with chronic conditions

Benefits Of Physical Activity

Physical activity can confer health benefits for adults and older adults living with the following chronic conditions:

- **For cancer survivors** – physical activity improves all-cause mortality, cancer-specific mortality, and risk of cancer recurrence or second primary cancer
- **For people living with hypertension** – physical activity improves cardiovascular disease mortality, disease progression, physical function, health-related quality of life
- **For people living with type-2 diabetes** – physical activity reduces rates of mortality from cardiovascular disease and indicators disease progression
- **For people living with HIV** – physical activity can improve physical fitness and mental health (reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression) and does not adversely affect disease progression (CD4 count and viral load) or body composition.

Recommendations

It is recommended that:

- All adults and older adults with the above chronic conditions should undertake regular physical activity
- Adults and older adults with these chronic conditions should do at least 150–300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 75–150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous intensity activity throughout the week for substantial health benefits.

For additional health benefits

- Adults and older adults with these chronic conditions should also do muscle-strengthening activities at moderate or greater intensity that involve all major muscle groups on 2 or more days a week, as these provide additional benefits.
- As part of their weekly physical activity, older adults with these chronic conditions should do varied multicomponent physical activity that emphasises functional balance and strength training at moderate or greater intensity on 3 or more days a week, to enhance functional capacity and prevent falls.

- When not contraindicated, adults and older adults with these chronic conditions may increase moderate intensity aerobic physical activity to more than 300 minutes; or do more than 150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous intensity activity throughout the week for additional health benefits.

Good Practice Statements

- When not able to meet the above recommendations, adults with these chronic conditions should aim to engage in physical activity according to their abilities.
- Adults with these chronic conditions should start by doing small amounts of physical activity and gradually increase the frequency, intensity, and duration over time.
- Adults with these chronic conditions may wish to consult with a physical activity specialist or health-care professional for advice on the types and amounts of activity appropriate for their individual needs, abilities, functional limitations/complications, medications, and overall treatment plan.
- Pre-exercise medical clearance is generally unnecessary for individuals without contraindications prior to beginning light- or moderate-intensity physical activity not exceeding the demands of brisk walking or everyday living.

Behaviours To Avoid

In adults, including cancer survivors and people living with hypertension, type-2 diabetes and HIV, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality and cancer mortality, and incidence of cardiovascular disease, cancer, and incidence of type-2 diabetes.

For cancer survivors, and adults living with hypertension, type-2 diabetes, and HIV, it is recommended that:

- Adults and older adults with chronic conditions should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.
- To help reduce the detrimental effects of high levels of sedentary behaviour on health, adults and older adults with chronic conditions should aim to do more than the recommended levels of moderate- to vigorous-intensity physical activity.

4.1.2.6 Children and adolescents (5-17 years old) living with disability

Benefits Of Physical Activity

Many of the health benefits of physical activity for children and adolescents, as set out in the section above, also relate to those children and adolescents living with disability. Additional benefits of physical activity to health outcomes for those living with disability include

- improved cognition in individuals with diseases or disorders that impair cognitive function, including attention-deficit/ hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)
- improvements in physical function may occur in children with intellectual disability

Recommendations

It is recommended that:

- Children and adolescents living with disability should do at least an average of 60 minutes per day of moderate- to vigorous intensity, mostly aerobic, physical activity, across the week.
- Vigorous-intensity aerobic activities, as well as those that strengthen muscle and bone should be incorporated at least 3 days a week.

Good Practice Statements

- Doing some physical activity is better than doing none.
- If children and adolescents living with disability are not meeting these recommendations, doing some physical activity will bring benefits to health.
- Children and adolescents living with disability should start by doing small amounts of physical activity and gradually increase the frequency, intensity, and duration over time.
- There are no major risks for children and adolescents living with disability engaging in physical activity when it is appropriate to an individual's current activity level, health status and physical function; and the health benefits accrued outweigh the risks.
- Children and adolescents living with disability may need to consult a health-care professional or other physical activity and disability specialist to help determine the type and amount of activity appropriate for them.

Behaviours To Avoid

In children and adolescents, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: increased adiposity; poorer cardiometabolic health, fitness, and behavioural conduct/pro-social behaviour; and reduced sleep duration.

It is recommended that:

- Children and adolescents living with disability should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary, particularly the amount of recreational screen time.

4.1.2.7 Adults (18+) living with disability

Benefits Of Physical Activity

Many of the health benefits of physical activity for adults, as set out in the section above, also relate to adults living with disability. Additional benefits of physical activity to health outcomes for those living with disability include the following:

- **For adults with multiple sclerosis** – improved physical function, and physical, mental, and social domains of health-related quality of life
- **For individuals with spinal cord injury** – improved walking function, muscular strength, and upper extremity function; and enhanced health-related quality of life
- **For individuals with diseases or disorders that impair cognitive function** – improved physical function and cognition (in individuals with Parkinson's disease and those with a history of stroke); beneficial effects on cognition; and may improve quality of life (in adults with schizophrenia); and may improve physical function (in adults with intellectual disability); and improves quality of life (in adults with major clinical depression).

Recommendations

It is recommended that:

- All adults living with disability should undertake regular physical activity.
- Adults living with disability should do at least 150–300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 75–150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity throughout the week for substantial health benefits.

For additional health benefits

- Adults living with disability should also do muscle-strengthening activities at moderate or greater intensity that involve all major muscle groups on 2 or more days a week, as these provide additional health benefits.
- As part of their weekly physical activity, older adults living with disability should do varied multicomponent physical activity that emphasises functional balance and strength training at moderate or greater intensity on 3 or more days a week, to enhance functional capacity and prevent falls.
- Adults living with disability may increase moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity to more than 300 minutes; or do more than 150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity throughout the week for additional health benefits

Good Practice Statements

- Doing some physical activity is better than doing none.
- If adults living with disability are not meeting these recommendations, doing some physical activity will bring benefits to health.
- Adults living with disability should start by doing small amounts of physical activity, and gradually increase the frequency, intensity, and duration over time.
- There are no major risks to adults living with disability engaging in physical activity when it is appropriate to the individual's current activity level, health status and physical function; and when the health benefits accrued outweigh the risks.
- Adults living with disability may need to consult a healthcare professional or other physical activity and disability specialist to help determine the type and amount of activity appropriate for them.

Behaviours To Avoid

In adults, higher amounts of sedentary behaviour are associated with the following poor health outcomes: all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality and cancer mortality and incidence of cardiovascular disease, cancer, and type-2 diabetes.

It is recommended that:

- Adults living with disability should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits.
- To help reduce the detrimental effects of high levels of sedentary behaviour on health, adults living with disability should aim to do more than the recommended levels of moderate to vigorous-intensity physical activity

4.1.3 Activity 2: Diet

The current studies supported that recommending an eating style can help people make positive changes. The benefits include prevention of cardiovascular disease, cancer, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and obesity.

We will perform an initial diet habit assessment for all participants. Our suggestions will be mainly according to the NHS Eatwell guide², American Family Physician Goals and Guidelines of Diets for Health³, and World Health Organisation⁴.

1. These dietary patterns are supported by strong evidence that promotes a primary focus on unprocessed foods, fruits and vegetables, plant-based fats and proteins, legumes, whole grains, and nuts.
2. Added sugars should be limited to less than 5% to 10% of daily caloric intake.
3. Vegetables (not including potatoes) and fruits should make up one-half of each meal.
4. Carbohydrate sources should primarily include beans/legumes, whole grains, fruits, and vegetables.
5. An emphasis on monounsaturated fats, such as olive oil, avocados, and nuts, and omega-3 fatty acids, such as flax, cold-water fish, and nuts, helps prevent cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and cognitive decline.
6. On average, women should have around 2,000 calories a day (8,400 kilojoules) and men should have around 2,500 calories a day (10,500 kilojoules).
7. Eat fruits, vegetables, legumes (e.g., lentils, beans), nuts and whole grains (e.g., unprocessed maize, millet, oats, wheat, brown rice) every day. The recommended daily intake for an adult includes: 2 cups of fruit (4 servings), 2.5 cups of vegetables (5 servings), 180 g of grains, and 160 g of meat and beans. Red meat can be eaten 1–2 times per week, and poultry 2–3 times per week.
8. Eat at least 5 portions of fruit and vegetables a day (at least 400 g). Potatoes, sweet potatoes, cassava and other starchy roots are not classified as fruit or vegetables.
9. Limit total energy intake from free sugars to around 12 level teaspoons (which is equivalent to 50 g). Most free sugars are added to foods or drinks by the manufacturer, cook or consumer, and can also be found in sugars naturally present in honey, syrups, fruit juices and fruit juice concentrates.
10. Limit total energy intake from fats to less than 30%. Unsaturated fats (e.g., found in fish, avocado, nuts, sunflower, canola and olive oils) are preferable to saturated fats (e.g. found in fatty meat, butter, palm and coconut oil, cream, cheese, ghee and lard). Industrially produced trans fats (found in processed food, fast food, snack food, fried food, frozen pizza, pies, cookies, margarines and spreads) are not part of a healthy diet.
11. Limit salt to less than 5 g per day (equivalent to approximately 1 teaspoon) (6) and use iodized salt

² <https://www.nhs.uk/live-well/eat-well/>

³ <https://www.aafp.org/afp/2018/0601/p721.html>

⁴ https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/325828/EMROPUB_2019_en_23536.pdf

4.1.4 Activity 3: Sleep

Some studies have reported that sleep duration was associated with certain types of cancer, although the association between sleep duration and subsequent cancer development still needs further studies to elucidate. Sleep is still crucial for physical, social, and mental well-being.

We will use Heathentia Mobile App to assess our participants' sleep pattern at the start and then provide the personalised recommendation followed by the NHS sleep suggestion⁵.

1. Go to bed at the same time and get up from bed at the same time every day.
2. Reduce or avoid sleeping during the day.
3. Take regular exercise during the day.
4. Limit or avoid caffeine, alcohol, and nicotine before bedtime
5. Avoid going to bed hungry or too full
6. Only use the bed for sleeping and sex
7. Don't take your problems to bed
8. Try to have a relaxing bedtime routine
9. Keep the bedroom quiet, dark and a comfortable temperature
10. Don't force yourself to try to go to sleep
11. Get regular exposure to natural light

⁵ <https://www.nhs.uk/media/.leaflets/61d8276e8d91a8.96413296.pdf>

5 Conceptual foundations for citizen's typology (segmentation) variables

At the heart of developing any segmentation approach is grouping individuals based on certain similar characteristics. The main principle of this grouping is to understand which group might be more or less likely to engage with a recommended behaviour (e.g., physical activity). Furthermore, if segmentation captures the most relevant personal characteristics, it should also provide understanding on how to best communicate with different groups, so that the communication (e.g., coaching) appeals to (matches) specific needs of each segment. If the coaching matches the needs of a person (from a given segment), then this person is more likely to engage with the recommended activities.

Figure 3 below represents the proposed conceptual foundations for citizen's typology. The framework proposes three main characteristics that are likely to impact acceptance of health behaviours: health goal orientation, health literacy and gender. Because all the recommended health behaviours (sections 4.1-4.3) if present impact citizen's health (in a positive way) and if absent have detrimental impact on health, one of the most relevant personalisation (segmentation) factor (i.e., personal characteristic that is likely to impact on adoption of such health recommendations) is the type of motivation one can have in relation to pursuing health goals. Hence health goal orientation differentiating individuals as predominantly promotion or prevention (see more detailed description in section 5.1.2) oriented towards health. The second factor that is most likely to impact acceptance of the recommended health behaviours is the level of health literacy one has. On a very simple level, we can differentiate individuals as having higher or lower levels of health literacy. Finally, gender has been found as an important factor in impacting acceptance of health behaviours, hence it is also part of the proposed segmentation framework. In the sections below we explain all the segmentation concepts and explain the principles and algorithms needed to clarify people into groups.

Figure 3: Conceptual foundations for citizen's typology

5.1 Health related goals and health behaviours

Any type of health recommendation resulting from pancreatic cancer risk assessment (as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2) will require an individual to set a goal to follow that specific recommendation (e.g., be more active, change diet, etc.). Goal setting and pursuit literature recognises the relevance of considering goal related motivations when supporting individuals who might be in the process of goal setting and later pursuit. Regulatory Focus Theory (RFT) recognises specific type of goal orientation and motivation that is relevant when it comes to goal setting and risk consideration. Hence, we propose this factor as a key one to consider in the personalisation approach.

5.1.1 Regulatory Focus Theory

Regulatory Focus Theory (RFT) has emerged from the field of cognitive psychology. RFT refers to when an individual pursues a goal, then they adhere to their personal values and beliefs, which is denoted as an individual's regulatory orientation (A., H., 03). RFT portrays the proposition that human beings are innately driven by two primary motivational states: promotion focus, and prevention focus while coping with strategies during goal pursuit to meet their specific needs (HIG., 98) (H., S., F., 97A). Individuals' promotion focus is grounded on their nurture-related needs (e.g., gains and advancements) and adopt approach strategies in life to seek opportunities for growth and achievements. Conversely, prevention-oriented individuals favour safety and security needs and follow vigilance strategies to safeguard from probable losses and threats to their personal wellbeing (HIG, 02). The idea of RFT has been predicated on the premise that individuals seek pleasure but also tend to avoid suffering. In general, a promotion focus is more associated with the presence or absence of positive outcomes, and a prevention focus is more associated with the presence or absence of negative outcomes (H., S., 04). RFT extends the basic notion of the hedonic principle by arguing that goal pursuit processes for an individual are driven by valence. The processes depend on everyone's inclination to quantify benefits vs losses (TAT, 02). RFT also highlights individual differences in adopting strategies pertinent to achieving respective goals. Consideration of individual differences is intricating but indispensable since promotion and prevention tenets have distinctive effects on consumer behaviour (L., C., J., 12).

5.1.2 Health Goal Orientation (Promotion or Prevention)

Individuals follow inherent processes that are in line with their motivational orientations during goal pursuit, and strategies individuals follow to achieve the goals. Human beings perceive goals as desired states that they strive to achieve and undesirable states that they strive to avoid; thus, either state of mind portrays individuals' internal and mental representation (B., P., H., +08). The term "goal orientation" emerged from social-cognitive literature, which refers to how an individual interprets and responds to tasks, resulting in distinct patterns of cognition, affect, and behaviour (D., L., 98). In general, goal orientation portrays either an individual's standings towards developing their own abilities for growth and advancement or exhibiting abilities required for accomplishment (VAN, 97). Scholars denoted these two basic goal orientations as learning orientation: the goal is developing abilities to perform tasks, and performance orientation: goal is demonstrating capabilities for positive evaluation (V., C., S., 01). Learning oriented individuals build their competencies by accepting challenges, and they perceive going through challenging phases as an opportunity for progress. On the contrary, performance-oriented individuals tend

to avoid tasks, which do not represent their abilities to complete the task, and there is a risk of failure. Another stream of research in goal orientation explored goal commitment and goal progress orientation (F., D., 05) (Z., F., D., 07). Individuals with goal commitment orientation are focused, and they pursue goals with uttermost efforts so that they do not deviate from achievement. In contrast, individuals with goal progress orientation perceive that they are closer to goal completion. This tendency devotes them to pursuing some other goals while also deviating from focal aims (S., D., C., 19). Individuals achieve regulatory fit when they pursue goals in ways that are consistent with their regulatory focus. Regulatory fit describes and enables individuals to "feel right" about their actions and increases participation in goal-directed behaviours (A., L., 06). Individuals feel motivated and confident of achieving an outcome when there is a regulatory fit, enabling them to take specific actions deliberately compared to when there is no fit. Thereby, Individuals are driven by various goal orientations that shape varied consumer behaviours for goal achievements.

The health goal orientation of individuals is significantly associated with their respective health outcome goals, which explains the activities to be performed to change lifestyle and overall wellbeing. To understand an individual's health goal orientation, consumer researchers commensurately utilised the premise of RFT that individuals either promotion or prevention focused during goal pursuit (G., B., P., 13). Successful completion of health goals by achieving intended health outcomes relies highly on individuals' motivation to get engaged in health-related behaviours (e.g., reducing stress, eating healthy, etc.). Individuals who are motivated by health gains reflect they are promotion focused. If they are motivated by evading health losses, then they are prevention focused; therefore, individuals' motivation and engagement depend on their respective regulatory focus (H., S., F., 97B). Therefore, individuals with a promotion or preventive orientation both have a desire to accomplish goals, but their definitions of goals and preferred methods of achieving goals differ.

Promotion oriented individuals are more driven towards achieving success and progressing growth. They are also more concerned about the presence or absence of anticipated outcomes. Communications to promotion focused individuals emphasising the benefits of compliance (e.g., daily physical activity will increase wellbeing) encourage the purpose of goal means to secure favourable outcomes, which establishes regulatory fit and behavioural engagement (L., R., R., +08A). Promotion driven individuals perceive success as a positive outcome and consider failure as non-gaining of a positive outcome.

Conversely, prevention-oriented individuals perceive goals as commitments to achieve, so they prefer to avoid them to ensure safety and security. Unlike promoters, preventers are more concerned about the presence or absence of unanticipated outcomes. Communications to prevention focused individuals emphasising the sacrifice of being noncompliant (e.g., poor health may cause from physical inactivity) encourage the purpose of goal means to avoid unfavourable outcomes which establish regulatory fit and behavioural change (L., R., R., +08B). Prevention driven individuals perceive success by avoiding a negative outcome and consider failure as not being able to avoid a negative outcome.

The distinction in goal orientations that individuals are either prevention or promotion focused may lead to pursuing a goal with different approaches and strategies (MAP, 08). Since individuals with the prevention or promotion orientation interpret and value goals differently, their approach to healthy behaviour will differ. Individuals with prevention and promotion focus are determined to achieve goals, but they will follow different strategies directed by their individual differences and respective goal orientation. We take

this notion and assume that an individual's health goal orientation, either promotion or prevention focused orientation, will lead to form their respective viewpoint towards adopting healthy behaviour. Scholarly research studies empirically exhibited that communications utilise promotion or prevention orientation significantly persuasive in various health contexts such as antismoking, weight management etc. (K., B., T., 10) (KIM, 06) (S., G., H., 04). In line with the literature and above discussions, we also postulate that an individual's health goal orientation (promotion or prevention) and congruent communication will motivate individuals to adopt healthy behaviour.

5.1.3 Measuring promotion or prevention goal orientation

To enable iHelp to recognise and categorise individuals accordingly to their health goal orientation, there is an established and validated measure that can be used. This measure, presented and explained in Table 2 below, can be used through a questionnaire or a chatbot or a coaching agent, where a citizen is provided with a list of statements (see below) and asked to judge their own assessment/level of agreement with each statement. Table 2, on the bottom, contains the information that is needed to translate the answers to the questionnaire, transform it into an actionable algorithm that will enable iHelp partners to differentiate between those with promotion or prevention health orientation.

Table 2. Measurement items and scoring criteria for estimating individual goal orientation

Please rate the following statements in line with your own beliefs
PM 1. If I succeed in reaching a health goal, this motivates me to go further. PM 2. I think that taking care of my health is pleasurable. PM 3. I see myself as someone who does my utmost to improve my health. PM 4. If I see a good opportunity to improve my health, I take advantage of it right away. PV 1. I frequently think about the health problems I may have in the future. PV 2. When I implement a health behaviour, it's because I want to protect myself from getting sick. PV 3. I often worry about mistakes I could make concerning my health.
Promotion Orientation (PM) refers to items capturing promotion orientation Prevention Orientation (PV) refers to items capturing prevention orientation Answers evaluated on a 5 item Likert scale (1-5 - strongly disagree to strongly agree) To differentiate individuals as predominantly promotion or prevention oriented, first we calculate their PM scores average, then PV score average, then we subtract PV from the PM score. If the resulting difference is greater than 0 - we categorise them as someone PM oriented, if the resulting difference is equal to or greater than 0 - we categorise them as someone PV oriented.

5.2 The role of health literacy

The basic concept of literacy has evolved over the last decade that highlighted the skill level of individuals and expanded beyond basic skillsets like speaking, writing, reading, technological, cultural etc., required to work and live in the society (A., R., 20). Theoretical dimensions of literacy have been expanded to encompass a broad range of skills so that an individual's increased knowledge impact positively the quality of life and wellbeing. In line with the extension and applicability of basic literacy, health literacy has also emerged that alleviates informed decision making of an individual about their own health. In general, health literacy is defined as the ability of an individual to access, process and comprehend associated health information and services to make effective health decisions (K., P., N., 04). Health literacy varies based on

the medical condition, the health care practitioner, and the institution delivering medical services. A satisfactory level of health literacy implies that an individual can use his or her literacy skills to understand health related communication associated with such as prescriptions, medical cards, medicine labelling-instructions, overarching health messages to all members of the society etc. (P., R., B., +95). Health literacy includes several aspects related to individuals and society. But the basic idea of health literacy does not highlight the broader aspect of literacy and meaning to people in their everyday life. According to Nutbeam (NUT, 02), health literacy portrays three basic dimensions: functional-the fundamental understanding of an individual about health information for their own and family; interactive-the communication between patients and health care service providers; critical-societal and political factors that influence the processing of information for public health decisions. Therefore, a holistic understanding of health literacy is prevalent since communicating health information will facilitate individuals and have ramifications on encouraging public health concerns, reducing health costs and overall health inequalities.

Health literacy is an integral component in public and personalised health communications. Empowerment of individuals hence patients in health context is a key priority for patient-centred healthcare that also admits the advantages of involving individuals in his or her health decision making (KAT, 02). Moreover, involving individuals in shared health decision-making drives initiatives related to substantial lifestyle change since individuals own the entire process wholeheartedly (C., D., S., 14). In a recent study, (S., W., C., 22) empirically exhibited that fluency in health communication induces consumer participation. Individuals transparently understand the decision with their involvement to achieve the goal, and consumers with higher literacy have higher fluency than lower literacy levels. Thereby, adequate health literacy is critical for becoming an active participant in one's healthcare decisions and management.

Scholars examined and emphasized the effect of health literacy level on various health related outcomes such as healthy behaviours, prevention, balanced diet etc. Individuals with a high degree of health literacy indicated more engagement in healthy physical exercise and eating a balanced diet (M., S., I., 16). Moreover, higher health literacy is identified as a key predictor for a healthy lifestyle since individuals possess more responsibilities for healthy food intake and regular physical exercises (Y., L., C., 17). Individuals with higher health literacy have higher knowledge and confidence as coping strategies to deal with chronic diseases (H., W., R., +15). Conversely, lower health literacy is interlinked with a lower level of health status because of higher usage of medical services usage, higher mortality, and lower level of noncompliance towards prescribed diets and physical activities (B., M., G., 04). Individuals with insufficient health literacy often lack a grasp of illness processes, have difficulty recalling and comprehending advice and instructions, hold health attitudes that obstruct treatment, and have poor problem-solving abilities (M., C., C., 05). Furthermore, according to Nutbeam (NUT, 17), health literacy plays a pivotal role in health promotion and prevention strategies since increased health literacy improves lifestyle to promote healthy behaviours. Therefore, depending upon the level of health literacy (higher or lower) individual's goal orientation and engagement for health behaviour differ.

5.2.1 Measuring health literacy

To enable iHelp to recognise and categorise individuals accordingly to their health literacy, there is an established and validated measure that can be used. This measure, presented and explained in Table 3 below, can be used through a questionnaire or a chatbot or a coaching agent, where a citizen is provided with a list of statements (see below) and asked to judge their own assessment/level of agreement with

each statement. Table 3, on the bottom, contains the information that is needed to translate the answers to the questionnaire, transform it into an actionable algorithm that will enable iHelp partners to differentiate between those with lower and higher health literacy.

Table 3. Measurement items and scoring criteria for estimating individual level of goal literacy

How easy would you say it is for you to...
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. find information on treatments of illnesses that concern you? 2. understand the leaflets that come with your medicine? 3. judge the advantages and disadvantages of different treatment options? 4. call an ambulance in an emergency? 5. find information on how to manage mental health problems like stress or depression? 6. understand why you need health screenings? 7. judge which vaccinations you may need? 8. decide how you can protect yourself from illness based on advice from family and friends? 9. find out about activities that are good for your mental well-being? 10. understand information in the media on how to get healthier? 11. judge which everyday behaviour is related to health? 12. join a sports club or exercise class if you want to?
<p>(1) Very easy, (2) Fairly easy, (3) Fairly difficult, (4) Very difficult, (0) Don't know</p> <p>To categorise individuals, we add all the items (do not know counted as 0) and split the sample by midpoint/median (this requires larger sample to estimate)</p>

5.3 The role of gender (Female or Male)

Gender comprises several characteristics that bring a categorization between male and female. Gender differences are prevalent, which play a critical role in understanding consumer behaviour. Male and females have distinct expectations, needs, wants and lifestyles, which influence their consumption patterns. Males and females differ in their responses for product decisions, and a significant difference in their information processing styles and factors that affect these reactions are intriguing in nature but uttermost important to understand for researchers and service providers (M., L., 15A). Primarily, males and females differ based on their physical appearances-abilities and the socio-cultural impact (W., E., 12). The fundamental differences are women's ability to birth and nurse children and men's speed and strength towards completing tasks efficiently. Socio-cultural beliefs emerged from the biological differences since birth and throughout developmental phases that males are dominant, possess better leadership traits, and can-do labour-intensive jobs. Females are kind in nature, responsible and have higher emotional intelligence. Male and female differences also appear in their self-regulation behaviour Females are found to be more responsive towards environmental cues and have a higher likelihood of accepting behavioural change interventions in an appropriate context congruent with their gender role (M., L., 15B). Another stream of research, evolutionary psychology (SAA, 17), also argues that males have higher aggression and inclinations towards adopting risk-taking behaviours than females, which portrays their self-status (E., D., L., +12). Research also highlighted key differences between gender in their responses towards marketing communication cues. Females are less favourable towards comparative advertisements, but males have

higher involvement that builds a positive perception about a product or service (CHA, 07). Indeed, these male and female distinctions expose challenging yet fascinating considerations to design behavioural change interventions irrespective of the contextual applications.

Scholars from various domains examined how to promote healthy behaviours, motivate individuals to adopt healthy behaviours, and why consumers perform regular or sporadically specific health-related behaviours, but very little is known how gender disparities form and affect the healthy behaviours practice of consumers (L., S., C. +19). Women search for health-related information and get involved with health behaviours more frequently compared to men (VER, 85). Moreover, due to natural differences in physical strength between gender, involvement with physical activities also differs (S., H., 90). Importantly, males have a higher probability of chronic diseases due to biological and lifestyle phenomena than females (C., M., M., 02). Extant research also articulated that women's healthier lives heavily rely on factors not limited to their social support, education, intensity-stress level of the job, etc. In contrast, men's health life significantly depends on their lifestyle choices such as food consumption and habitual practices such as alcohol and smoking intake (D., S., F., +07). Therefore, due to generic and context specific differences between gender, it is also prevalent that motivation hence goal orientation will also differ between males and females towards healthy behaviours. The preceding discussion highlights gender differences for explicating consumer behaviour, and we also construe why males and females would respond differently because of their respective gender differences. We build upon this belief and contend that an individual's health goal orientation (promotion or prevention) will influence their health behaviours, and this effect will differ between gender. Therefore, we posit that gender moderates the relation between an individual's goal orientation and healthy behaviour.

6 Empirical validation of the proposed typology (segmentation)

To examine feasibility of the proposed framework in the context of acceptance of physical activity recommendations data was collected from 500 adults in the UK. The study was designed prior to iHelp project and was not part of the project. Therefore, we report only the results most relevant to the project here. Raw data are not available to the project partners. The questionnaire contained a list of quantitative measures to capture respondents' goal orientation, level of health literacy, gender, etc. The questionnaire also asked participants to provide answers in writing in relation to the most prevalent motivation and barriers to engage in health behaviours.

The quantitative data were analysed with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This is a method used to evaluate how different groups of people (as specified by our segmentation variables) behave in relation to the desired activity (here, physical activity as a health behaviour). The main framework for data analysis is illustrated in Figure 3 above.

Qualitative data were analysed with Natural Language Processing (NLP) approach, a branch of AI that is concerned with giving computers the ability to understand text in the same way as humans can. NLP combines computational linguistics—rule-based modelling of human language—with statistical, machine learning, and deep learning models. Together, these technologies enable computers to process human language in the form of text or voice data and to 'understand' its full meaning, complete with the speaker or writer's intent and sentiment. NLP drives computer programs that translate text from one language to another, respond to spoken commands, and summarise large volumes of text rapidly—even in real time. In the current work, NLP was used to summarise the motives and barriers in relation to undertaking health behaviours. This approach is like a traditional thematic analysis approach (in relation to text) when large amounts of text are analysed in search of common meanings and patterns.

6.1 Relevant questions

To capture health goal orientation and level of health literacy we used the list of questions listed in Tables 2 and 3. To verify gender of research participants they were asked to specify their gender (male, female or other). Majority of participants self-described as male or female, with several cases selecting the "other" option. Considering the very small number of "other" categories, the data analysis considered only males and females, those who selected "other" were excluded from the analysis.

To capture the main outcome (dependent) variable, participants were asked the question presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Measurement of the main outcome (dependent variable) – physical activity

<p>Please think about your everyday behaviours <u>over the last month</u> and answer the questions below.</p> <p>"Over the last month how often have you made a conscious effort to "</p> <p>6a. improve your health in general</p> <p>6b. eat healthy food</p> <p>6c. be more active (i.e., engage in some type of physical activity)</p>

6d. improve length and/or quality of your sleep

6e. reduce stress

1= Never – 5 = Daily

For analysis, we considered only the answer in relation to physical activity.

6.2 Typology validation

To analyse the data and evaluate the impact of the proposed segmentation variables of the main dependent variable we performed Factorial ANOVA. The model tested the relationships illustrated in Figure 3 above. Factorial ANOVA enables us to verify the main as well as interaction effects of the three proposed independent variables (health goal orientation, health literacy and gender). We controlled for the effects of income, age, region, and education (see Figure 3). The main and interaction effects are presented in Table 5 below. The shaded row presents an interaction effect. To interpret the results, we consider the size of F statistics and its associated p value. While main effects (e.g., goal orientation or gender alone) can be large and significant, a significant interaction effects shows dependency of the effects, pointing to superiority of recognising interaction (vs main) effects.

While we observe a significant main effect of goal orientation, we can also observe a significant interaction effect, confirming the relevance of all the proposed segmentation factors. The illustration of the interaction effects is presented below, in Figure 4 and 5.

Table 5. Results of Factorial Analysis of Variance summarising main and interaction effects of goal orientation, gender and health literacy on the recommended behaviour

Dependent Variable	Effects	F-Value	Sigma	Power
Be more active	Goal orientation	52.662	$p < .001$	1.000
	Gender	1.288	$p = .225$.228
	Health literacy	2.857	$p = .092$.393
	Goal orientation Gender Health literacy	7.243	$p = .007$.766
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Results of goal orientation, gender and health literacy on the recommended behaviour controlling for (including in the model) age, education, income, and region 				

Figure 4 illustrates the interaction between goal orientation and health literacy for females, while Figure 5 illustrates the interaction between goal orientation and health literacy for males. Interestingly, promotion-oriented individuals tend to engage less with physical activity than promotion-oriented individuals. Health literacy is a positive factor for prevention-oriented females and does not seem to have a great effect in prevention-oriented males. Interestingly, while increased health literacy impacts active participation in physical activity for males, it is not a necessary condition for females, who tend to perform better regarding physical activity when having lower levels of health literacy.

Those findings point to the fact that using coaching and personalising it so that different type of knowledge/coaching is presented in a way to motivate different segments could be an effective way to bring about the desired behaviour change in individuals.

Estimated Marginal Means of Please think about your everyday behaviours over the last month and answer the questions below.
"Over the last month how often have you made a conscious effort to " - Be more active (i.e., engage in some type of physical activity)

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: What is the approximate annual income of your household (before deductions)? = 7.76, What is the highest level of education you have completed? - Selected Choice = 3.55, What region are you from? = 6.90, What is your age?
 Write your answer using the text box below = 52.3890

Figure 4: Results of Factorial Analysis of Variance for females.

Estimated Marginal Means of Please think about your everyday behaviours over the last month and answer the questions below.
"Over the last month how often have you made a conscious effort to " - Be more active (i.e., engage in some type of physical activity)

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: What is the approximate annual income of your household (before deductions)? = 7.76, What is the highest level of education you have completed? - Selected Choice = 3.55, What region are you from? = 6.90, What is your age?
 Write your answer using the text box below = 52.3890

Figure 5: Results of Factorial Analysis of Variance for males.

6.3 Recognising motivations and barriers to adoption of healthy behaviours - Text analysis

The main purpose of the text analysis was to identify common themes that would summarise the perceptions of motivations and barriers for different groups, as defined by the identified segmentation variables. The text analyses were carried on four main clusters:

1. Prevention oriented with low health literacy
2. Prevention oriented with high health literacy
3. Promotion oriented with low health literacy
4. Promotion oriented with high health literacy

The results of topic modelling for motives are presented in Figures 7, 8, 11 and 12 and a breakdown of the main topics by gender is presented in Figures 9 and 10.

6.3.1 Topic modelling of qualitative data

Topic modelling is an unsupervised machine learning method for scanning a set of documents, detecting word and phrase patterns, and automatically clustering word groups and related phrases that best describe a set of documents using probabilistic modelling.

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is an approach for topic modelling that classifies or categorises the text in a document and the words per topic using Dirichlet distributions and processes.

The LDA makes two key assumptions:

- Documents are a mixture of topics, and
- Topics are a mixture of tokens (or words)

These topics using the probability distribution generate the words. Statistically, the documents are known as the probability density (or distribution) of topics and the topics are the probability density (or distribution) of words.

Figure 6: Topic modelling approach used to analyse qualitative data.

Once the topic distribution for each document is identified, the dominant topic for each document is the one where it falls the highest, which is used to conclude the thematic analysis of that user.

6.3.2 Motives to engage in healthy behaviours: Identified topics and split by gender

The following dominant topics have been identified using the LDA model. The table below is an example to demonstrate how the model provides a panoramic view of how these texts get modelled by showing the original text, identifying keywords, and categorising the dominant topic of these sentences which focus on the reasons why the users made a conscious effort to be healthy.

Health Reason: Segment 1		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
Having tea usually means I want something to accompany it and it's usually chocolate or biscuits as fruit and tea don't really match	['tea', 'usually', 'want', 'accompany', 'usually', 'chocolate', 'biscuit', 'fruit', 'tea', 'really', 'match']	Snacky Habits
I think cravings for sweet things and my husband who doesn't stop buying it.	['think', 'crave', 'sweet', 'thing', 'husband', 'stop', 'buy']	(Topic 0)
Healthy behaviours need to also be stimulating and fun where possible. For example, diets should use tasty and exciting ingredients rather than bland, tasteless ones.	['behaviour', 'also', 'stimulate', 'fun', 'possible', 'example', 'diet', 'use', 'tasty', 'exciting', 'ingredient', 'rather', 'bland', 'tasteless']	Mundane Health Related Activities
Boredom, habit eating. The fact that I am so grossly overweight and the task to get down to a reasonable weight is a huge one, which will likely take a couple of years.	['boredom', 'habit', 'eat', 'fact', 'grossly', 'overweight', 'task', 'get', 'reasonable', 'weight', 'huge', 'likely', 'take', 'couple', 'year']	(Topic 1)
I'm one of those people for whom forming a habit is hard and breaking it is a case of one or two missed opportunities or a couple of bad events. Simply getting up late and having to rush out the door can break healthier behaviours for me and leave me playing catch up not just for that day, but possibly several days to a week after. More than one event where I have to put myself second in close proximity and I can easily lose progress on developing a healthy habit. The good part of this is bad habits are just as hard to	['people', 'form', 'habit', 'hard', 'breaking', 'case', 'miss', 'opportunity', 'couple', 'bad', 'event', 'simply', 'get', 'late', 'rush', 'door', 'break', 'behaviour', 'leave', 'play', 'catch', 'day', 'possibly', 'several', 'day', 'week', 'event', 'put', 'second', 'close', 'proximity', 'easily', 'lose', 'progress', 'develop', 'habit', 'good', 'part', 'bad', 'habit', 'hard', 'form']	Domino Effect of Breaking Healthy Habits
Drinking alcohol and eating junk food distract me from going further with my healthy behaviors. I enjoy the simple and quick reward and these temptations can be hard to resist.	['drink', 'alcohol', 'eat', 'junk', 'food', 'distract', 'go', 'behavior', 'enjoy', 'simple', 'quick', 'reward', 'temptation', 'hard', 'resist']	(Topic 2)

Health Reason: Segment 2		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
No time to exercise as working all day and looking after out kids the rest of the time. I could eat better but often don't have much time and want comfort food. I'm not sleeping well because of my 3 year old.	['busy', 'day', 'day', 'hard', 'find', 'time', 'exercise', 'also', 'difficult', 'eat', 'healthier', 'balanced', 'meal', 'short', 'time']	Time Crunch due to Multi-Tasking
Being very busy day to day meaning it's harder to find the time for exercise. It is also more difficult to eat more healthier and balanced meals when I am short of time	['time', 'main', 'distraction', 'easy', 'say', 'time', 'exercise', 'really', 'well', 'time', 'management']	(Topic 0)
Depression, prescription medications and pain killers e.g. gabapentin, codeine, naproxen - makes me dizzy and dopey and sleepy.	['depression', 'prescription', 'medication', 'pain', 'killer', 'make', 'dizzy', 'dopey', 'sleepy']	Medication induced inadequacies
Social media, tiredness, anxiety, pain, depression	['social', 'medium', 'tiredness', 'anxiety', 'pain', 'depression']	(Topic 1)
I am sometime thrown off course from healthy behaviours by 'awarding' myself treats which are usually bad for me such as potato crisps, chocolate and alcohol.	['sometime', 'throw', 'course', 'behaviour', 'awarding', 'treat', 'usually', 'bad', 'potato', 'crisp', 'alcohol']	Affinity to Desserts and Losing Willingness Due to Boredom
Often healthy behaviours are boring. It's difficult to say no good is Better than a big bowl of ice cream. So I'll often lose my willingness to suffer healthiness and once I've lost it a little it's hard to get back.	['often', 'behaviour', 'bore', 'difficult', 'say', 'good', 'big', 'bowl', 'ice', 'cream', 'often', 'lose', 'willingness', 'suffer', 'healthiness', 'lose', 'little', 'hard', 'get', 'back']	(Topic 2)

Figure 7: Topic Modelling for motives for people who lie in Segment 1 and Segment 2.

Health Reason: Segment 3		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
Sometimes I feel the need to cheer myself up and have a habit of eating unhealthy food in an attempt to feel better	['sometimes', 'feel', 'cheer', 'habit', 'eat', 'unhealthy', 'food', 'attempt', 'feel', 'well']	Emotional Eating
When I'm feeling down.	['feel']	(Topic 0)
Instant gratification - like sweets, or a movie. Low-effort activities which promise pleasant rewards.	['instant', 'gratification', 'sweetie', 'movie', 'low', 'effort', 'activity', 'promise', 'pleasant', 'reward']	Indulgence for Instant Gratification
chocolate is tastier than the healthy options, and feeling lazy stops me exercising as much as I should.	['tasty', 'option', 'feel', 'lazy', 'stop', 'exercise', 'much']	(Topic 1)
the convenience of "unhealthy" food so things like crisps and sandwiches are just so quick and easy, not to mention cheap.	['convenience', 'unhealthy', 'food', 'thing', 'crisp', 'sandwich', 'quick', 'easy', 'mention', 'cheap']	Stress Eating and Lack of Willpower
It's very difficult to avoid comfort eating when bored or stressed. Also difficult to find the willpower to avoid sugary snacks.	['difficult', 'avoid', 'comfort', 'eat', 'bored', 'stress', 'also', 'difficult', 'find', 'willpower', 'avoid', 'sugary', 'snack']	(Topic 2)

Health Reason: Segment 4		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
Demands of my time on others is the main distraction. Being grandfather and childminder its easy for family members to require my time thus potentially preventing me to use my time to exercise.	['demand', 'time', 'main', 'distraction', 'grandfather', 'childminder', 'easy', 'family', 'member', 'require', 'time', 'thus', 'potentially', 'prevent', 'use', 'time', 'exercise']	Giving up Exercise for Family Commitments
I am a full-time mum so I do a lot of walking but exercise of my choice has to be a conscious effort after making sure the children have what they need and are being cared for.	['full', 'time', 'mum', 'lot', 'walk', 'exercise', 'choice', 'conscious', 'effort', 'make', 'sure', 'child', 'need', 'care']	(Topic 0)
I enjoy visiting coffee shops, socially, and cannot resist a good scone or slice of cake	['enjoy', 'visit', 'coffee', 'shop', 'socially', 'resist', 'good', 'scone', 'slice', 'cake']	Social Eater
Poor will power, impulsive food choices. Laziness. Socialising during the evening with friends.	['poor', 'power', 'impulsive', 'food', 'choice', 'laziness', 'socialise', 'evening', 'friend']	(Topic 1)
After over a decade of regular exercise I would be lying if I said I didn't get bored of it on occasion. The same repetitive routines (more or less) lose their effectiveness eventually and become staid.	['decade', 'regular', 'exercise', 'lie', 'say', 'get', 'bored', 'occasion', 'repetitive', 'routine', 'le', 'lose', 'effectiveness', 'eventually', 'become', 'staid']	Ineffective Exercise Routine
My phone distracts me from healthy behaviours. I am a morning person and feel much better when I get up early, do some exercise and get things done. But I have a tendency to get sidetracked by my phone sometimes which can make me feel a bit rubbish.	['phone', 'distract', 'behaviour', 'morning', 'person', 'feel', 'much', 'well', 'get', 'early', 'exercise', 'get', 'thing', 'tendency', 'get', 'sidetrack', 'phone', 'sometimes', 'make', 'feel', 'bit', 'rubbish']	(Topic 2)

Figure 8: Topic Modelling for motives for people who lie in Segment 3 and Segment 4.

Segment 1 : Prevention Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Topic Theme

Segment 2 : Prevention Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of Users by Topic Theme

Figure 9: Motives – User Distribution for each topic in the Segment 1 and 2.

Segment 3 : Promotion Oriented with Low Health Literacy
Number of Users by Topic Theme

Segment 4 : Promotion Oriented with High Health Literacy
Number of Users by Topic Theme

Figure 10: Motives – User Distribution for each topic in the Segment 3 and 4.

Segment 1 : Prevention Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender MF

Gender ... ● 1 ● 2

Segment 2 : Prevention Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

Segment 3 : Promotion Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

Segment 4 : Promotion Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

*Gender 1 refers to Female and Gender 2 refers to Male

Figure 11: Motives – user distribution based on topic and gender.

6.3.3 Barriers to engage in healthy behaviours: Identified topics and split by gender

Similarly, the table below is an example to demonstrate how these barriers to being healthy get modelled by showing the original text, identifying keywords, and categorising the dominant topic of these sentences.

Health Reason: Segment 1		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
Because I realised how unfit I am and I want to be around for a long time to watch my children grow up and be a part of their lives	['realise', 'unfit', 'want', 'long', 'time', 'watch', 'child', 'grow', 'part', 'life']	Increasing Life Expectancy (Topic 0)
As I reach middle age, I realised that my body was starting to show signs of the effects of smoking. As well as cost, I decided to try and stop using tobacco. I succeeded. With regard to alcohol, I had Gastritis for a period, and alcohol was stopped and never resumed.	['reach', 'middle', 'age', 'realise', 'body', 'start', 'show', 'sign', 'effect', 'smoke', 'well', 'cost', 'decide', 'try', 'stop', 'use', 'tobacco', 'succeed', 'period', 'alcohol', 'stop', 'never', 'resume']	Motivated due to Pandemic (Topic 1)
I was drinking far too much alcohol due to stress and loneliness due to covid lockdowns and self isolating because of a compromised immune system	['drink', 'far', 'much', 'alcohol', 'due', 'stress', 'loneliness', 'due', 'covid', 'self', 'compromise', 'immune', 'system']	Motivated due to illness (Topic 2)
COVID and having to work from home more.	['covid', 'work', 'home']	
My wife decided to be pescatarian so it seemed sensible to join in, however I do eat a small amount of meat. Red meat can be unhealthy cholesterol not to mention anti biotics and hormones that can be in meat. I decided it was a good change for my health	['wife', 'decide', 'seem', 'sensible', 'join', 'however', 'eat', 'small', 'amount', 'meat', 'red', 'meat', 'unhealthy', 'cholesterol', 'mention', 'anti', 'biotic', 'hormone', 'meat', 'decide', 'good', 'change']	
a close family friend recently found out that they had throat cancer and was more than likely caused by smoking	['close', 'family', 'friend', 'recently', 'find', 'throat', 'cancer', 'likely', 'cause', 'smoking']	

Health Reason: Segment 2		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
The water and sodium goal is because of this kidney function issue I have. It's borderline as being chronic kidney disease. That is scary to me! I'm losing weight because I was looking fat, was uncomfortable and worried I could develop diabetes etc because of it.	['water', 'sodium', 'goal', 'kidney', 'function', 'issue', 'borderline', 'chronic', 'kidney', 'disease', 'scary', 'lose', 'weight', 'look', 'fat', 'uncomfortable', 'worried', 'develop', 'diabetes']	Asked by Physician (Topic 0)
Being able to purchase a book by a doctor I trust for a reduced price (part of a deal)	['able', 'purchase', 'book', 'doctor', 'reduce', 'price', 'part', 'deal']	
I'm overweight and will be 60 years old in October. I want to improve my health before then	['overweight', 'year', 'old', 'want', 'improve']	Quality of Life (Topic 1)
This was mainly to help me concentrate more, and to try and live more in the moment, as well as try and reduce stress and anxiety	['mainly', 'help', 'concentrate', 'try', 'live', 'moment', 'try', 'reduce', 'stress', 'anxiety']	
I was worried about my husbands high blood pressure, lack of exercise and heart attack risk. I also felt I needed some exercise as i'm working from home so no longer cycling to work.	['worried', 'husband', 'high', 'blood', 'pressure', 'lack', 'exercise', 'heart', 'attack', 'risk', 'also', 'feel', 'need', 'exercise', 'work', 'from', 'home', 'long', 'cycle', 'work']	Motivated by illness (Topic 2)
['acid', 'reflux', 'arthritis', 'high', 'cholesterol', 'active', 'thyroid']	Acid Reflux, Arthritis, High cholesterol and over active Thyroid	

Figure 12: Topics for barriers who people in Segment 1 and Segment 2.

Health Reason: Segment 3		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
Firstly due to health and prevention of any complications, also environmental consideration as well as last but not least economic reasons, although we like to support local businesses as best we can. not a lot	['firstly', 'due', 'prevention', 'complication', 'also', 'environmental', 'consideration', 'well', 'last', 'least', 'economic', 'reason', 'support', 'local', 'business', 'good', 'lot']	Health Related Complication
April 2019, 2 x cardiac arrests out of hospital	['arrest', 'hospital']	(Topic 0)
I've been having problems with my sleep quality for some time, and knew it was sinus-related, but not what it was. Through a process of elimination I discovered I have a mild reaction to mouthwash which affects my sinus for a short time, and was harming the quality of my sleep.	['problem', 'sleep', 'quality', 'time', 'know', 'sinus', 'relate', 'process', 'elimination', 'discover', 'mild', 'reaction', 'mouthwash', 'affect', 'sinus', 'short', 'time', 'harm', 'quality', 'sleep']	Quality of Sleep
It was the knowledge that it wasn't doing me any good. As much as I like regular caffeinated coffee, it was affecting me negatively and the result was unhealthy.	['knowledge', 'good', 'much', 'regular', 'caffeinate', 'coffee', 'affect', 'negatively', 'result', 'unhealthy']	(Topic 1)
I'm conscious of how damaging sugar is to the body, and concerned about the amount of it that is put in food.	['main', 'reason', 'lose', 'weight', 'change', 'thinking']	Unhealthy Eating Habits
Cut out the crap, stopped drinking alcohol and exercising more.	['cut', 'crap', 'stop', 'alcohol', 'exercise']	(Topic 2)

Health Reason: Segment 4		
Text from User	Text Keywords	Topic Theme
I wanted to make a healthy change because I had put a little weight on and had always weighed the same since the age of 18 and did not enjoy seeing a change in my body shape. Also, because I have a sweet tooth and had out weight on due to over-indulging in sweet snacks I began to not enjoy too many sweet things. I also see myself as not very disciplined at times so wanted to show myself that I could be disciplined for a more positive outcome.	['want', 'make', 'change', 'put', 'little', 'weight', 'always', 'weigh', 'age', 'enjoy', 'see', 'change', 'body', 'shape', 'also', 'sweet', 'tooth', 'weight', 'due', 'indulge', 'sweet', 'snack', 'begin', 'enjoy', 'many', 'sweet', 'thing', 'also', 'see', 'discipline', 'time', 'want', 'show', 'discipline', 'positive', 'outcome']	Weight Gain Due to Sweet Tooth
I knew I needed to lose weight. My BMI was in the obese category and I was worried I was going to become diabetic and I didn't want to be on medication.	['know', 'need', 'lose', 'weight', 'worry', 'become', 'diabetic', 'want', 'medication']	(Topic 0)
My husband was diagnosed with menieres which has changed our diet and life style, less salt, alcohol and caffeine, all food freshly cooked. This we combined with walking. Given my family history of stroke I decided that regular exercise and healthy eating would benefit us both.	['husband', 'diagnose', 'life', 'style', 'salt', 'alcohol', 'caffeine', 'food', 'freshly', 'cook', 'combine', 'walk', 'give', 'family', 'history', 'stroke', 'decide', 'regular', 'exercise', 'eat', 'benefit']	History of illness in family
After a relationship breakdown I decided I needed to improve my physical and mental health. Exercise gave me structure to my evenings and improved my physical and mental health	['relationship', 'breakdown', 'decide', 'improve', 'physical', 'mental', 'exercise', 'give', 'structure', 'evening', 'improve', 'physical', 'mental']	(Topic 1)
I was a stone overweight (according to the BMI index) and my blood pressure was around 140/80	['stone', 'overweight', 'accord', 'index', 'blood', 'pressure']	Being Overweight
I was at my heaviest and didn't feel well or happy with my appearance	['heavy', 'feel', 'well', 'happy', 'appearance']	(Topic 2)

Figure 13: Topics for barriers in Segment 3 and Segment 4.

Segment 1 : Prevention Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Topic Theme

Segment 2 : Prevention Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of Users by Topic Theme

Figure 14: Barriers – User Distribution for each topic in the Segment 1 and 2.

Segment 3 : Promotion Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Topic Theme

Segment 4 : Promotion Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of Users by Topic Theme

Figure 15: Barriers – User Distribution for each topic in the Segment 3 and 4.

Segment 1 : Prevention Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

Segment 2 : Prevention Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

Segment 3 : Promotion Oriented with Low Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

Segment 4 : Promotion Oriented with High Health Literacy

Number of Users by Dominant Topic and Gender

Gender ● 1 ● 2

*Gender 1 refers to Female and Gender 2 refers to Male

Figure 16: Barriers – User Distribution for each topic in each segment by gender.

7 Proposed personalisation approaches for the iHelp platform

Considering the review of all the relevant factors that can contribute to personalisation of pancreatic cancer risk mitigation, we developed iHelp personalisation framework, as illustrated in the table 6 below. It is important to stress that this framework considers risk assessment as an intervention that can support goal setting in relation to the iHelp recommended behaviour (e.g., physical activity). The framework presented in table 6 proposes the use of AI toolbox to profile iHelp users and design different coaching message content that will impact acceptance of the iHelp recommendation for different groups. The assumption is that the coaching dialogue facilitating goal setting takes place after individual undergoes pancreatic cancer risk assessment. Some examples of coaching dialogues are presented in section 8 of this deliverable.

Table 6: Proposed personalisation framework for iHelp platform

User Characteristics	AI Toolbox for Personalization	Coaching message content for different groups facilitating goal setting (where the goal is to follow the iHelp recommendation)
Age	AI rules and algorithms segmenting individuals and recommending certain elements of content to different groups accordingly	Highlight desirable intervention outcomes framing
Gender		Highlight health benefits framing
Health goal orientation (promotion or prevention)		Highlight cue to action frame
Health literacy		Different intensity of the recommended behaviour
Whether user smokes or not		Different level of difficulty of the recommended behaviour
Whether user lives with chronic conditions or not (WHO defines chronic conditions as being a cancer survivor, having hypertension, type 2 diabetes, or HIV)		

Whether user lives with a disability		
Whether user is a pregnant or postpartum woman		
User’s level of engagement with a specific behaviour		

It is important to stress that some of the user characteristics will be relevant for profiling across a range of recommended health behaviours (e.g., goal orientation, health literacy, gender). This is because these are some motivational and ability characteristics that are psychological characteristics of users in relation to health behaviours in general. Other user characteristics – e.g., smoking, living with chronic condition or not, are user characteristics that relate to a specific recommended health behaviour.

While development of this framework and current deliverable rests with recommending uptake of physical activity, it is important to recognise there are other health behaviours that will reduce individual risk of pancreatic cancer. These behaviours include introducing healthier diet, quitting smoking, etc.

To ensure that the content of the recommended messages (see table 6 above and table 8 below) fits perceptions, motivations, and abilities of different segments, it is also necessary to evaluate the starting point of engagement with the recommended behaviour. This is mainly to ensure personalised message that is less likely to cause stress and anxiety in case the recommended activity exceeds someone ability. A potential measure evaluating individual level of engagement with different activities is presented in Table 7 below. We can also utilise any user data that will be available and tracked with different sensors available through the iHelp platform.

Table 7: Measure to use to evaluate the starting point of engagement with the recommended behaviour

<p>Please think about your everyday behaviours <u>over the last month</u> and answer the questions below.</p> <p>"Over the last month how often have you made a conscious effort to "</p> <p>6a. improve your health in general 6b. eat healthy food 6c. be more active (i.e., engage in some type of physical activity) 6d. improve length and/or quality of your sleep 6e. reduce stress</p> <p>(1) never, (2) rarely, (3) about half of the time, (4) most of the time, (5) daily</p>

Table 8 below illustrates the proposed element of content messages to be designed to target different segments of iHelp users. It is important to note that these are ideas in the process of development and the final personalisation framework will be tested and validated during the duration of the project.

Table 8: Proposed coaching message content for the iHelp platform for different groups/segments

Type of physical activity	Promotion high health literacy	Promotion low health literacy	Prevention high health literacy	Prevention low health literacy
Desirable intervention outcomes framing	Feel look good	Feel look good	Avoid illness	Avoid illness
Desirable intervention outcomes framing	Gain improvement	Gain improvement	Maintain status quo	Maintain status quo
Desirable intervention outcomes framing	Feel rewarded Achieve gains	Feel rewarded Achieve gains	Avoid any losses	Avoid any losses
Health benefits framing	Recommended to do OR For additional benefit OR recommended to avoid	Recommended to do OR For additional benefit OR recommended to avoid	Recommended to do OR For additional benefit OR recommended to avoid	Recommended to do OR For additional benefit OR recommended to avoid
Cue to action frame	Improve/excel	Improve/excel	Follow recommendations / guidelines	Follow recommendations / guidelines
Cue to action frame	Accomplish	Accomplish	Stay safe	Stay safe
Intensity of the recommended behaviours	Start with average involvement / intensity / frequency of the recommended behaviour	Start with low involvement / intensity / frequency of the recommended behaviour	Start with average involvement / intensity / frequency of the recommended behaviour	Start with low involvement / intensity / frequency of the recommended behaviour
Ease of the recommended behaviours	Start with average difficulty behaviours	Start with simple behaviours	Start with average difficulty behaviours	Start with simple behaviours
User Experience (UX) factors:	Green associated with health OR yellow associated	Green associated with health OR yellow associated	Green associated with health OR yellow associated	Green associated with health OR yellow

colour of answer option buttons	with warmth and clarity OR yellow associated with enthusiasm and cheerfulness	with warmth and clarity OR yellow associated with enthusiasm and cheerfulness	with warmth and clarity OR yellow associated with enthusiasm and cheerfulness	associated with warmth and clarity OR yellow associated with enthusiasm and cheerfulness
UX and colour in user journey	Use of colour to point to a journey/sequence	Use of colour to point to a journey / sequence	Use of colour to point to a journey / sequence	Use of colour to point to a journey / sequence
UX: gender of the coaching agent	Male, female, or gender neutral			
UX: chat presentation	Simple dialogue or dialogue with more detailed/graphical background	Simple dialogue or dialogue with more detailed / graphical background	Simple dialogue or dialogue with more detailed / graphical background	Simple dialogue or dialogue with more detailed / graphical background

8 Developing dialogues in the context of recommending physical activity

The current section proposes a sample of dialogue messages that could be used during the process of goal setting (where the goal is to follow the iHelp recommendation, e.g., be more physically active).

It is important to recognise that such goal setting dialogues are most likely to take place after the pancreatic cancer risk assessment. This is because the risk assessment acts as an intervention to facilitate and support goal setting.

The dialogue examples are based on WHO recommendations and guidelines for only one of the groups identified in section 4.1.2 – healthy adults 18-64 years old (see section 4.1.2.2). As most of the recommendation contain a minimum time limit spent engaging with a given activity (e.g., minutes of 150 minutes of moderate physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous physical activity for healthy adults – for definition of activities please see Table 1 in section 4.1.1), the recommended time allocation can be further adapted for different groups described in section 4.1.1.

Furthermore, to account for different levels of difficulty of the recommended activities, the coaching dialogues involve a possible range of activities users can choose from (basic recommended behaviours, behaviours recommended for additional health benefits, behaviours recommended to avoid – see section 4.1.2.2)

8.1 Dialogue settings

The following section gives an example of coaching dialogues initiated by a coaching agent (A) and potential answers alternatives to be given to users to choose from (U). While in a typical dialogue a user just types in an answer (like shown in illustration in Figure xx below), in iHelp a user will be provided with some options (e.g., U1) to choose to respond to the coaching agent.

The personalisation conditions and content examples are labelled in the following way:

- Coaching agent questions/suggestions (A)
- User choice alternatives (U)

Numbers in relation to the coaching dialogues (e.g., A1 and U1) indicate the order of questions and show matching set of dialogues (e.g., there might be more than one U1 – that will correspond to a specific A1)

- *PV - framing for prevention-oriented individuals in italics*
- PM - framing for promotion-oriented individuals in underlined format

Sections in bold explain specific segment characteristics (e.g., PM with low or high health literacy).

Figure 17: A dialogue illustration. Online illustration by Storyset.

8.2 Dialogue scenarios

A1: Based on your risk profile I can recommend some activities that will help you to reduce the risk of future disease and make you look and feel better.

Would you like me to help you set up your personalised plan?

A1: Based on your biological profile I can recommend some activities that will help you to improve your health and make you look and feel better.

Would you like me to help you set up your personalised plan?

U1: Yes >> A3

U1: Not sure >> A2

U1: No

A2: Did you know that even some small changes to your lifestyle (e.g., walking or avoiding certain foods) can help you to avoid various diseases and could enable you to enjoy longevity and fuller mobility for longer?

Should we see how I can help you to introduce those changes?

A2. Did you know that even some small changes to your lifestyle (e.g., walking or avoiding certain foods) can help you to improve your health and enable you to enjoy longevity and fuller mobility for longer?

Should we see how I can help you to introduce those changes?

U2: Yes, let's give it a try >> A3

U2: No, thanks >> end

If user not active, PV- low health literacy

A3: What would you like to *try* first?

People in this specific category need a very careful encouragement as they might feel anxious if recommendation feels like it exceeds their abilities.

U3: Let's try to introduce some physical activity into your weekly routine >> A4

U3: Let's try to introduce some healthier eating habits into your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's try to introduce some physical activity and healthy diet into your weekly routine >> a mix of A4 and A5

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: Sorry, I am not interested >> end

If user active, PV- high literacy, PM - low literacy

A3: What would you like to *do/achieve* first?

U3: Let's make physical activity part of your weekly routine >> A4

U3: Let's make healthier eating habits part of your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's make some physical activity and healthy diet part of your weekly routine >> a mix of A4 and A5

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: I think I do all I should be doing already and do not need your help >> reinforce personalised approach that might be different than someone is already practicing

U3: Sorry, I am not interested

If user not active, PV -high literacy, PM - low literacy

A3: What would you like to *do/achieve* first?

U3: Let's make physical activity part of your weekly routine >> A4 (but might need to aim for more than the minimum time from the guidelines)

U3: Let's make healthier eating habits part of your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's make some physical activity and healthy diet part of your weekly routine >> a mix of A4 and A5

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: Sorry, I am not interested

If user active, PM- high literacy:

A3: What would you like to achieve first?

U3: Let's improve how you benefit from physical activity by integrating it fully into your weekly routine >> A7

U3: Lets improve how you benefit from healthier diet by integrating it fully into your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's improve how you benefit from physical activity and healthy diet by integrating it fully into your weekly routine >> A7 & A5

U3: I think I do all I should be doing already and do not need your help >> reinforce personalised approach that might be different than someone is already practicing

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: Sorry, I am not interested

*A4: Did you know that for best health outcomes **adults like you** are recommended at least 150 minutes of moderate physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous physical activity **per week**.*

Examples of moderate physical activity include:

- Walking at fast pace
- Cleaning (e.g., vacuuming, mopping)
- Mowing lawn
- Bicycling
- Playing badminton or tennis doubles

Examples of vigorous physical activity include

- Hiking
- Jogging
- Shovelling
- Carrying heavy loads
- Bicycling fast
- Playing a basketball or soccer game
- Playing tennis singles

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

A4: Did you know that **adults like you** who get best health results tend to exceed the recommended minimum of 150 minutes of moderate physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous physical activity **per week**.

Examples of moderate physical activity include:

- Walking at fast pace
- Cleaning (e.g., vacuuming, mopping)
- Mowing lawn
- Bicycling
- Playing badminton or tennis doubles

Examples of vigorous physical activity include

- Hiking
- Jogging
- Shovelling
- Carrying heavy loads
- Bicycling fast
- Playing a basketball or soccer game
- Playing tennis singles

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

U4: Yes, please!

U4: Can I do less? >> Doing some physical activity is better than doing none. Let's start with xx min of xx activity.

U4: Can I do more? I think I already meet the requirements! >> take to muscle strengthening advice>> A7

U4: I think I would rather start with another health behaviour >> A3

U4: No, sorry, this is not for me

A5: Did you know that for best health outcomes **adults like you** are recommended to consume on average 2000 /2500⁶ calories **a day**.

It is recommended that you stay within the recommended calorie intake and try to:

- Eat fruits, vegetables, legumes (e.g., lentils, beans), nuts and whole grains (e.g., unprocessed maize, millet, oats, wheat, brown rice) every day. The recommended daily intake for an adult includes: 2 cups of fruit (4 servings), 2.5 cups of vegetables (5 servings), 180 g of grains, and 160 g of meat and beans. Red meat can be eaten 1–2 times per week, and poultry 2–3 times per week.
- Eat at least 5 portions of fruit and vegetables a day (at least 400 g). Potatoes, sweet potatoes, cassava and other starchy roots are not classified as fruit or vegetables.

⁶ Differences in recommendations due to gender

- Limit total energy intake from free sugars to around 12 level teaspoons (which is equivalent to 50 g). Most free sugars are added to foods or drinks by the manufacturer, cook or consumer, and can also be found in sugars naturally present in honey, syrups, fruit juices and fruit juice concentrates.
- Limit total energy intake from fats to less than 30%. Unsaturated fats (e.g., found in fish, avocado, nuts, sunflower, canola and olive oils) are preferable to saturated fats (e.g., found in fatty meat, butter, palm and coconut oil, cream, cheese, ghee and lard). Industrially produced trans fats (found in processed food, fast food, snack food, fried food, frozen pizza, pies, cookies, margarines and spreads) are not part of a healthy diet.
- Limit salt to less than 5 g per day (equivalent to approximately 1 teaspoon) (6) and use iodized salt

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

A5: Did you know that **adults like you** who get best health results tend consume on average 2000 /2500 calories **a day**.

For best health results stay within the recommended calorie intake and try to:

- Eat fruits, vegetables, legumes (e.g., lentils, beans), nuts and whole grains (e.g., unprocessed maize, millet, oats, wheat, brown rice) every day. The recommended daily intake for an adult includes: 2 cups of fruit (4 servings), 2.5 cups of vegetables (5 servings), 180 g of grains, and 160 g of meat and beans. Red meat can be eaten 1–2 times per week, and poultry 2–3 times per week.
- Eat at least 5 portions of fruit and vegetables a day (at least 400 g). Potatoes, sweet potatoes, cassava and other starchy roots are not classified as fruit or vegetables.
- Limit total energy intake from free sugars to around 12 level teaspoons (which is equivalent to 50 g). Most free sugars are added to foods or drinks by the manufacturer, cook or consumer, and can also be found in sugars naturally present in honey, syrups, fruit juices and fruit juice concentrates.
- Limit total energy intake from fats to less than 30%. Unsaturated fats (e.g., found in fish, avocado, nuts, sunflower, canola and olive oils) are preferable to saturated fats (e.g., found in fatty meat, butter, palm and coconut oil, cream, cheese, ghee and lard). Industrially produced trans fats (found in processed food, fast food, snack food, fried food, frozen pizza, pies, cookies, margarines and spreads) are not part of a healthy diet.
- Limit salt to less than 5 g per day (equivalent to approximately 1 teaspoon) (6) and use iodized salt

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

U5: Yes, can we start with reducing my sugar intake first?

U5: Yes, can we start with reducing my intake of processed foods?

U5: Yes, can we start to follow all the recommendations?

U5: Yes, can I first define exactly what I want to eat and avoid eating?

U5: I think I would rather start with another health behaviour >> A3

U5: No, sorry, this is not for me

A7: Did you know that for best health outcomes **adults like you** are recommended

- *up to 300 minutes of moderate physical activity or 150 minutes of vigorous physical activity **per week**.*
- *at least 2 days a week engage with muscle-strengthening activities*

Examples of moderate physical activity include:

- Walking at fast pace
- Cleaning (e.g., vacuuming, mopping)
- Mowing lawn
- Bicycling
- Playing badminton or tennis doubles

Examples of vigorous physical activity include

- Hiking
- Jogging
- Shovelling
- Carrying heavy loads
- Bicycling fast
- Playing a basketball or soccer game
- Playing tennis singles

Examples of muscle-strengthening activities:

- lifting weights
- working with resistance bands
- heavy gardening, such as digging and shovelling
- climbing stairs
- hill walking
- cycling
- dance
- push-ups, sit-ups, and squats
- yoga

A7: Did you know that **adults like you** who get best health results tend to

- exceed the recommended minimum of 300 minutes of moderate physical activity or 150 minutes of vigorous physical activity **per week**.
- at least 2 days a week engage with muscle-strengthening activities

Examples of moderate physical activity include:

- Walking at fast pace
- Cleaning (e.g., vacuuming, mopping)
- Mowing lawn
- Bicycling
- Playing badminton or tennis doubles

Examples of vigorous physical activity include

- Hiking
- Jogging
- Shovelling
- Carrying heavy loads
- Bicycling fast
- Playing a basketball or soccer game
- Playing tennis singles

Examples of muscle-strengthening activities:

- lifting weights
- working with resistance bands
- heavy gardening, such as digging and shovelling
- climbing stairs
- hill walking
- cycling
- dance
- push-ups, sit-ups and squats
- yoga

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

- U7: Yes, please!
- U7: Can I do less? >> Doing some physical activity is better than doing none. Let's start with xx min of xx activity.
- U7: Can I do more? I think I already meet the requirements!
- U7: I think I would rather start with another health behaviour >> A3
- U7: No, sorry, this is not for me

8.3 A sample dialogues

This section illustrates a sample dialogue for low health literacy, PV group

A1: Based on your risk profile I can recommend some activities that will help you to reduce the risk of future disease and make you look and feel better.

Would you like me to help you set up your personalised plan?

U1: Yes >> A3

U1: Not sure >> A2

U1: No

A2 Did you know that even some small changes to your lifestyle (e.g., walking or avoiding certain foods) can help you to avoid various diseases and could enable you to enjoy longevity and fuller mobility for longer?

Should we see how I can help you to introduce those changes?

U2: Yes, let's give it a try >> A3

U2: No, thanks >> end

If user not active, PV- low health literacy

A3: What would you like to try first?

People in this specific category need a very careful encouragement as they might feel anxious if recommendation feels like it exceeds their abilities.

U3: Let's try to introduce some physical activity into your weekly routine >> A4

U3: Let's try to introduce some healthier eating habits into your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's try to introduce some physical activity and healthy diet into your weekly routine >> a mix of A4 and A5

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: Sorry, I am not interested >> end

If user active, PV- high or low literacy,

A3: What would you like to do first?

U3: Let's make physical activity part of your weekly routine >> A4

U3: Let's make healthier eating habits part of your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's make some physical activity and healthy diet part of your weekly routine >> a mix of A4 and A5

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: I think I do all I should be doing already and do not need your help >> reinforce personalised approach that might be different than someone is already practicing

U3: Sorry, I am not interested

If user not active, PV -high literacy

A3: What would you like to do first?

U3: Let's make physical activity part of your weekly routine >> A4 (but might need to aim for more than the minimum time from the guidelines)

U3: Let's make healthier eating habits part of your weekly routine >> A5

U3: Let's make some physical activity and healthy diet part of your weekly routine >> a mix of A4 and A5

U3: I don't think this will work as I am not good with introducing healthy habits >> A2

U3: Sorry, I am not interested

A4: Did you know that for best health outcomes **adults like you** are recommended at least 150 minutes of moderate physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous physical activity **per week**.

Examples of moderate physical activity include:

- Walking at fast pace
- Cleaning (e.g., vacuuming, mopping)
- Mowing lawn
- Bicycling
- Playing badminton or tennis doubles

Examples of vigorous physical activity include

- Hiking
- Jogging
- Shovelling
- Carrying heavy loads
- Bicycling fast
- Playing a basketball or soccer game
- Playing tennis singles

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

U4: Yes, please!

U4: Can I do less? >> Doing some physical activity is better than doing none. Let's start with xx min of xx activity.

U4: Can I do more? I think I already meet the requirements! >> take to muscle strengthening advice>> A7

U4: I think I would rather start with another health behaviour >> A3

U4: No, sorry, this is not for me

A5: Did you know that for best health outcomes **adults like you** are recommended to consume on average 2000 /2500⁷ calories **a day**.

It is recommended that you stay within the recommended calorie intake and try to:

⁷ Differences in recommendations due to gender

- Eat fruits, vegetables, legumes (e.g., lentils, beans), nuts and whole grains (e.g., unprocessed maize, millet, oats, wheat, brown rice) every day. The recommended daily intake for an adult includes: 2 cups of fruit (4 servings), 2.5 cups of vegetables (5 servings), 180 g of grains, and 160 g of meat and beans. Red meat can be eaten 1–2 times per week, and poultry 2–3 times per week.
- Eat at least 5 portions of fruit and vegetables a day (at least 400 g). Potatoes, sweet potatoes, cassava, and other starchy roots are not classified as fruit or vegetables.
- Limit total energy intake from free sugars to around 12 level teaspoons (which is equivalent to 50 g). Most free sugars are added to foods or drinks by the manufacturer, cook or consumer, and can also be found in sugars naturally present in honey, syrups, fruit juices and fruit juice concentrates.
- Limit total energy intake from fats to less than 30%. Unsaturated fats (e.g., found in fish, avocado, nuts, sunflower, canola, and olive oils) are preferable to saturated fats (e.g., found in fatty meat, butter, palm and coconut oil, cream, cheese, ghee, and lard). Industrially produced trans fats (found in processed food, fast food, snack food, fried food, frozen pizza, pies, cookies, margarines, and spreads) are not part of a healthy diet.
- Limit salt to less than 5 g per day (equivalent to approximately 1 teaspoon) (6) and use iodized salt

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

U5: Yes, can we start with reducing my sugar intake first?

U5: Yes, can we start with reducing my intake of processed foods?

U5: Yes, can we start to follow all the recommendations?

U5: Yes, can I first define exactly what I want to eat and avoid eating?

U5: I think I would rather start with another health behaviour >> A3

U5: No, sorry, this is not for me

A7: Did you know that for best health outcomes **adults like you** are recommended

- up to 300 minutes of moderate physical activity or 150 minutes of vigorous physical activity **per week**.
- at least 2 days a week engage with muscle-strengthening activities

Examples of moderate physical activity include:

- Walking at fast pace
- Cleaning (e.g., vacuuming, mopping)
- Mowing lawn
- Bicycling
- Playing badminton or tennis doubles

Examples of vigorous physical activity include

- Hiking
- Jogging
- Shovelling
- Carrying heavy loads

- Bicycling fast
- Playing a basketball or soccer game
- Playing tennis singles

Examples of muscle-strengthening activities:

- lifting weights
- working with resistance bands
- heavy gardening, such as digging and shovelling
- climbing stairs
- hill walking
- cycling
- dance
- push-ups, sit-ups, and squats
- yoga

I am sure you already are on track to meet the requirements. Should we help you with this challenge?

- U7: Yes, please!
- U7: Can I do less? >> Doing some physical activity is better than doing none. Let's start with xx min of xx activity.
- U7: Can I do more? I think I already meet the requirements!
- U7: I think I would rather start with another health behaviour >> A3
- U7: No, sorry, this is not for me

9 Validation and implementation of the proposed personalisation approaches

The proposed approaches (as proposed in the personalisation framework presented in Table 6) will be fine-tuned with feedback achieved from other consortium partners and verified in further tests. It is important to ensure the content of the messages is not making iHelp users uncomfortable, anxious or show signs of reactance (act against the specific health recommendation). All these results could emerge following health recommendations, hence it is very important to ensure that the message content is appropriate for users.

A way to test such approaches is to employ a large-scale experimental study where different groups of individuals are exposed to different messages and different combinations of messages. This could mean that a specific dialogue between an agent (A1) and user (U1) is evaluated in an experimental scenario. We could evaluate potential responses to such dialogues (e.g., levels of acceptance, user (U) dialogue choice preferences, various feelings resulting from exposure to the recommendation and the overall effectiveness and acceptance of the goal setting intervention).

Following such an extensive testing and validation, the entire personalisation framework as presented in Table 6 will be implemented within the iHelp platform in the T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanism for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback”). Furthermore, the approach will be further optimised by collaboration with T5.5 (“Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms”), which will enable us to monitor performance of different segments, optimise health recommendations based on actual behaviour of iHelp users, and consequently improve the developed personalisation approaches.

10 Summary and conclusions

10.1 Summary of the Deliverable

This deliverable reports the results achieved by the first half of Task 5.2 (“Design of personalised prevention and intervention measures”). The task aims to ensure that the pancreatic cancer risk assessment intervention is delivered in a personalised way and thus allows for an increased precision of the risk assessment intervention, increased likelihood of acceptance of the intervention (e.g., uptake of healthy behaviours that are likely to reduce one’s risk of developing pancreatic cancer), and overall reduction of pancreatic cancer incidents among citizens. We also aim to ensure iHelp software will be developed in alignment with the requirements stipulated in relation to developing personalised behaviour change interventions that are safe and effective for users.

This report reviews the state of art in health systems personalisation and AI approaches, define key principles of segmentation and personalisation approaches, provides an overview of the methodology to develop the proposed framework. Our state-of-the-art iHelp personalisation framework proposes designing of an AI toolbox that will capture the identified user characteristics, segment individuals into groups, and deliver personalised and motivating recommendations and communications that will encourage goal setting and pursuit. By goal setting and pursuit, we mean uptake of the recommended health behaviour (e.g., physical activity or diet) that is likely to reduce one’s risk of future cancer. This work leads to the first set of personalisation approaches that are currently being further developed and will be validated and then implemented in the iHelp platform. The final, verified, and optimised framework as well as its effectiveness (in personalisation and safety) is left for the second deliverable of T5.2, D5.5 due to be released in M32 (August 2023).

10.2 General guidelines for personalisation approaches in iHelp

Our proposed personalisation framework is presented in Table 6. The framework proposes the use of AI toolbox to profile iHelp users and design different coaching message content that will impact acceptance of the iHelp recommendation for different groups. The assumption is that the coaching dialogue facilitating goal setting takes place after individual undergoes pancreatic cancer risk assessment. The proposed framework recognises the following:

- Personalised and AI driven pancreatic cancer risk assessment as an intervention to drive behaviour change in iHelp users
- AI rules and algorithms segmenting individuals and recommending certain elements of content to different groups accordingly
- User characteristics that are relevant to capture for segmentation and personalization approaches for any health behaviour in the context of pancreatic risk assessment. These characteristics include health goal orientation, health literacy, level of engagement with a given health behaviour, age, and gender.
- User characteristics that are relevant to recognise in the context of a specific recommended behaviour, for example whether user lives with chronic conditions or not (WHO defines chronic conditions as being a cancer survivor, having hypertension, type 2 diabetes, or HIV), whether user

lives with disability or is a pregnant or postpartum woman are factors that should be recognised in the context of recommending physical activity.

- Content of AI driven communications should highlight the following factors:
 - Desirable intervention outcomes framing appropriate for different groups
 - Health benefits framing appropriate for different groups
 - Cue to action framing appropriate for different groups
 - Different level of difficulty of the recommended behaviour appropriate for different groups
 - Different level of intensity of the recommended behaviour appropriate for different groups
 - Different elements of User Experience (UX) characteristics of iHelp user interfaces appropriate for different groups

10.3 Future work

The entire personalisation framework will be first validated, then implemented within the iHelp platform in the T5.3 (“Delivery Mechanism for Personalised Healthcare and Real-Time Feedback”). Furthermore, the approach will be further optimised by collaboration with T5.5 (“Monitoring, Alerting, Feedback and Evaluation Mechanisms”), which will enable us to monitor performance of different segments, optimise health recommendations based on actual behaviour of iHelp users, and consequently improve the developed personalisation approaches.

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List of Acronyms

ADHD	Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
CA	Consortium Agreement
CRC	Colorectal Cancer
D	Deliverable
DAMA	Diet, Physical Activity, And Mammography
DoA	Description Of Action
EML	Epigenetic Mutation Load
EU	European Union
GP	General Practitioner
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
LDA	Latent Dirichlet Allocation
LXS	LeanXcale
MET	Metabolic Equivalent of Task
NHS	National Health Service
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PM	Promotion Orientation
PROCAS	Predicting Risk of Cancer at Screening
PRS	Protocol Registration and Results System
PV	Prevention Orientation
RCT	Randomized Control Trial
RFT	Regulatory Focus Theory
TV	Television
UNIMAN	University Of Manchester
UX	User Experience
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package